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MASTER OF RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT MANAGEMENT

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**AN ANALYSIS OF PERSONAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FACTORS AFFECTING
THE RESEARCH PRODUCTIVITY OF
GENERAL SURGERY TRAINING PROGRAMS IN THE PHILIPPINES**

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16 May 2024

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Acceptance Page

This Special Problem titled: “**AN ANALYSIS OF PERSONAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FACTORS AFFECTING THE RESEARCH PRODUCTIVITY OF GENERAL SURGERY TRAINING PROGRAMS IN THE PHILIPPINES**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Research and Development Management.

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Biographical Sketch

Professor Ida Marie Tabangay - Lim, MD is Chair of the Department of Clinical Epidemiology at the University of Santo Tomas Faculty of Medicine & Surgery and Chair of the Department of Surgery at Jose R. Reyes Memorial Medical Center.

She finished BS Biology and later Doctor of Medicine at the University of Santo Tomas. She did her General Surgery Residency in the same institution and underwent sub specialization in Head and Neck Surgery at the University of the Philippines - Philippine General Hospital in 2000 and completed a UICC-ICRETT scholarship to undergo clinical research fellowship in Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center in New York in 2004.

She got accepted as a faculty at the UST – Faculty of Medicine and Surgery in 2005 starting as Instructor 5 and gradually got promoted to Professor 2 in 2020 and to Professor 5 in 2022.

She completed the Diploma course in Research and Development Management of the UP Open University in 2014 and went on to take a Masters in R&DM in 2021.

Professor Ida Lim has written, presented, and published scientific articles on her topics of interest: thyroid, head and neck cancer, and surgical training among

others She is the project lead in the development of two national clinical practice guidelines –the Philippine Thyroid Cancer CPG 2021 and the Philippine Head and Neck Cancer CPG 2023 which have been included on the DOH compendium of CPGs. She is also part of the consensus panel of the Philippine Breast Cancer CPG and the CPG on Hyperthyroidism.

Professor Ida Marie Lim has been involved in the training of General Surgery residents since 2001, training of head and neck surgeons since 2005 and surgical oncologists since 2013. She has been a Board of Director of the Philippine Society of General Surgeons (2016-2019) and currently the Chair of the PSGS National Committee on Research. She is part of various committees under the Philippine College of Surgeons, Past president of the Philippine Academy for Head and Neck Surgery, Inc , Secretary of the Philippine Association of Training Officers in Surgery and Secretary of the Philippine Thyroid Association.

She has received recognition for her efforts in improving research. She received the PCS MMC Knights of the Knife Award for Research in 2022 and the UST FMS Alumni Association Thomas Awards for Research in 2023.

Dr. Lim is married to an orthopedic surgeon Dr. Nelson T. Lim, and they have a daughter, Mary Cristine Angela Lim, who is currently in UP College of Medicine.

DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

1. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MR&DM except where indicated in the Preface.
2. Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used.
3. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies, and appendices.

A handwritten signature in black ink, reading "Ida Marie T. Lim", enclosed in a thin black rectangular border.

Ida Marie T. Lim, MD

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	Dr. Orlando Ocampo (BOR)

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Dedication

To my family, husband Dr. Nelson Lim and daughter Mary Cristine Angela T. Lim

To mother Luz Tabangay and father (deceased) Hermoso C. Tabangay

To my aunt Ederlina Mendoza

To my colleagues, co-consultant, and resident trainees under the Philippine Society of General Surgeons

To co-directors and co-fellows of the Philippine Association of Training Officers in Surgery

To colleagues and co-fellows in the Philippine College of Surgeons

To co students, co-learners and faculty of the UP Open University Faculty of Management and Development Studies Program of Research and Development Management

To UST Faculty of Medicine & Surgery co -faculty especially the Department of Clinical Epidemiology and Department of Surgery

To our students in the UST Faculty of Medicine & Surgery

To our patients

To the Filipino

To God almighty for His providence , all glory and honor is offered in His name

Abstract

Research as an essential part of surgical training and healthcare systems has helped shape health policies and contributed to the overall improvement of health outcomes and the quality of healthcare. Although research has been required in surgical training programs which are unique R&D organizations and potential collaborators in the nation's strategic STI framework, there is a general perception that research productivity has not been fully optimized with very few research getting to be published and utilized. The surgical training programs' knowledge of facilitators and barriers to research productivity can help implement measures to motivate the institutions and their trainees to engage in relevant research which can contribute to the Philippine Development Plan (2023-2028).

In line with the Philippine Development Plan, and in support of Pagtanaw 2050, this study seeks to determine personal and institutional factors which promote research productivity among General Surgery trainees as an initial step towards improving R&D within the surgical community.

Utilizing mixed method research - sequential exploratory approach which involves an analytical cross section followed by a focus group discussion (FGD), we were able to gather 1014 responses from the residents (99%) and 58 responses (81.69%) from research coordinators of accredited General Surgery programs. The attitude towards research is positive overall. Although 85.9% have ongoing research, only 48% had the chance to present their research in a forum and only 29.5% were able to publish. Results show that an institution's affiliation with DOH and a higher level of surgical training were associated with more productive research practices. On

the other hand, among the barriers identified include: lack of dedicated research time (59.9%); difficult IRB process (11.9%) and lack of interest (8.7%).

Knowledge of the factors affecting research productivity is useful to the organization in implementing strategies which can assist the institutions in pursuing relevant and quality research publications and in improving research utilization.

Keywords: general surgery, research productivity, R&D

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Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

With the advent of technology, research has led to ground-breaking developments in the field of medicine and surgery. Research findings have been utilized and applied in the healthcare system to improve the management of disease conditions and their outcomes. However, sustainability in terms of the publication of relevant research which promotes societal and global development requires not only the individual researcher's commitment and passion to do research but also an infrastructure which can support the needs of the researcher and the institution (Reyes, J., 1995).

The World Health Organization together with national leaders share this goal of achieving sustainable development amidst challenges across the globe. This resulted to "17 Sustainable Development Goals [SDGs] with 169 integrated and indivisible targets". Goal No. 17 specifically "seeks to strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development" and has included Science and Technology among its targets (United Nations, 2024). The importance of science-based decision-making has been emphasized by including in their implementation plan ways to integrate the scientists' advice into decision-making bodies, improved collaboration between natural and social scientists and use of integrated scientific assessments among many others "and urged support for publicly funded research and development entities to engage in strategic alliances for the purpose of enhancing research and development" (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs). This provides an understanding that each government

may set their own targets and decide how these will be incorporated in national planning processes and strategies. In the same light, academic institutions and their affiliate healthcare systems with specialized training programs may also identify their targets, including those for R&D in support of the SDG's (CHED Memorandum Order no. 052-16, Oct 3, 2016).

The continuing gap in the level of advancement in the field of science & technology between the Philippines and other more advanced nations has been considered as a major challenge and the reason the country is slow in improvement with regards to inclusive growth and competitiveness. The need to address this gap is the main goal of Pagtanaw 2050, which is based on an assessment of major trends in science, technology and innovation in the country and includes health systems among its 12 operational areas (transnastphl.2021.1792). In support of the goal of Pagtanaw 2050, the Philippine Development Plan for 2023 – 2028 (National Economic Development Authority, 2023) included a strategy framework to advance research and development, technology, and innovation. Among the challenges identified in this plan include: “inadequate human resources in science-technology-innovation (STI), and R&D; and underdeveloped research culture and productivity.”

Looking at the Philippine healthcare system, specifically in the field of Surgery, there are 71 regular accredited General Surgery training programs in the year 2023 under the Philippine Society of General Surgeons, Inc. (PSGS). This can be considered high-yielding grounds for research and development, technology and innovation but perceived to have underdeveloped research culture and productivity. Through the implementation of a standard research program, creation of a national surgical research agenda, and collaborative research engagements, these training institutions have the potential to produce relevant research that can address

knowledge gaps in the management of different surgical conditions in the country. However, before this can be achieved, there is still a need to evaluate the current status of research productivity among these training programs and identify the factors which promote and limit research publication and concomitant utilization. Only a minority of graduate surgical trainees are able to present and publish their work in scientific and peer-reviewed journals in spite of the research requirement during training. In addition to that, there are also limited research collaborations between institutions in the country. Factors leading to this may include, but are not limited to a failure to stimulate the creativity of the surgeon as a scientist or innovator (Cuyno, 2003), lack of defined organizational structure (Cuyno, R & Garcia, P, 2003) or the lack of developed support systems which could nurture the culture of research (Reyes, J., 1995). Moreover, the diverse backgrounds and structure of surgical training programs in the Philippines may also affect research productivity among general surgeons in the country.

There is a need to determine these factors and come up with plausible solutions to improve the R&D performance of surgical training programs.

Statement of the Problem

Although the curriculum of General Surgery training programs has included research requirements for promotion and graduation, for the past several years, there is a general perception that publication of research remains unfulfilled even after completion of training program requirements. Due to an increased amount of time allotted for clinical work in surgical training programs, the time dedicated for R&D processes, which include time to conduct, complete and publish relevant research work, is greatly affected. The research requirement in effect leads to an unproductive

utilization of personal and institutional resources (time, finances, logistics). Hence, there is a need to re- evaluate the research capability and productivity of these training institutions, investigate the factors affecting their research productivity and improve the use of resources to produce relevant research that will be useful to society. There is a need to answer these questions:

- In terms of research presentation and publication among General Surgery training programs in the country, what is the status of their research productivity?
- What are the factors that affect research productivity in the General Surgery training programs?
- How can research productivity be improved in General Surgery training programs?

Objectives of the Study

The study generally aims to evaluate the research productivity of accredited General Surgery training programs in the Philippines.

Specifically, it intends to:

1. Identify personal and institutional factors which may be associated with research productivity among accredited General Surgery Training programs.
2. Compare the research productivity of different categories of General Surgery training programs.
3. Analyze the factors which affect research productivity of surgical trainees and training programs; and
4. Formulate a research program/curriculum proposal that can potentially improve research productivity of trainees and General Surgery training programs in the Philippines.

Significance of the Study

Engaging surgical residents and young faculty in various research endeavors, and cultivating their creativity and innovativeness (Cuyno, 1997) are essential to develop future academic leaders who have the capacity to improve the quality of patient care through research and innovation. However, research within a surgical training program entails the use of resources – human, time, financial and others for it to prosper. It would be useful for the surgical specialty organization, particularly PSGS, to recognize and analyze the facilitators and barriers to research productivity so as to create a framework of support, encourage research collaborations and implement strategies that could assist and motivate the institutions and their trainees to engage in relevant and quality research publications and improved research utilization which can have an impact on surgical care and national policies and contribute to societal development (Cuyno, Strategic R&D Management).

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study included all residents in accredited General Surgery training programs in the country which may or may not have any subspecialty program existing within that institution. These are tertiary healthcare institutions based on DOH classification. These institutions have been included as they have the basic resources for the conduct of research, including an Ethics board. Primary and secondary hospitals which may not be equipped with the basic research infrastructure were not included in the conduct of this study.

Random sampling of residents from each level of training was done. Due to conflicts in the schedule of these residents, having a face-to-face interview with them

proved to be difficult. Hence, focus group discussions (FGDs) were done online via Zoom.

A member of the research committee or training committee from each program was asked to answer the questionnaire. Out of 71 accredited programs, there were 58 responses gathered. They were also included in the FGD.

The investigator is the sole provider of funds for the study. No funding from any private or government institution was acquired to eliminate bias.

The investigator sent some correspondence to the PSGS, the organization in charge of the implementation of the General Surgery curriculum as well as the accreditation of the training programs, to inquire about the current status of the curriculum regarding research as well as the statistics on the annual research completed by the programs. Based on the annual report of the training programs, one can also have an idea regarding the number of publications per institution.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Review of Literature

Research and Development within General Surgery Training program

Research and Development (R&D) is considered essential in the healthcare system. There is a need for continuous knowledge generation and its application to help improve patient management outcomes. In a healthcare institution, R&D, which is done to improve the institution's productivity in terms of revenues is different from the research generated and utilized to promote innovations and improvement in health care services.

Research is considered a major driving force of advancement in the field of medicine and surgery. Many research contributions have been applied in healthcare to improve healthcare outcomes. As such, ensuring that scientific research remains as an integral aspect of surgical residency training programs is critical to the sustainability of the field. Furthermore, it is beneficial to have research as a mandatory component of graduate medical training programs (Laupland et al 2021; Stehlik et al 2020). Knowledge of research applications such as evidence-based medicine helps the trainees to have an improved understanding of and ability to apply evidence reported in the literature to their actual patients, which may in turn translate to improved clinical evaluation and patient outcomes. Research outputs by trainees could also help answer knowledge gaps and contribute generalizable data which may be useful in the management of certain disease conditions. In addition, research productivity during surgical training has been shown to improve the likelihood of being

accepted into advanced training positions and can ensure success in subsequent academic careers (Andriole et al 2020; Fladie et al 2023). More importantly, if we get to motivate researchers in each institution and initiate capacity building, this can be the start of collaborative research initiatives on the common surgical conditions of the country, thereby contributing to the establishment of national data which can fuel more research, leading to improvements of clinical care outcomes.

Surgery is a rigorous field not only in clinical practice but more importantly during training. There have been evolutionary changes in training from the 20th to the 21st century with shifting priorities and limited resources. A cohort study among surgical residents found that research productivity did not deteriorate over time despite work hour reforms, resident operative experience, duration of resident training, and patient care (Elliott, 2009). At the same time, it suggests that careful scrutiny of resident research productivity is needed to ensure productive academic surgeons in the future.

The demands of clinical training pose difficulties that such structured research writing programs may be challenging to implement simultaneously. Forrester et al (2017) described the potential impact of publishing on a resident's future career to encourage the design of formal writing programs for residents and in turn, facilitate or encourage their future commitment to research endeavors.

Policies which support R&D in training and academic programs

Since 1994, the Accreditation Council for Graduate Medical Education (ACGME) functions as an independent, non-profit organization that sets and monitors voluntary professional educational standards essential in preparing physicians to deliver safe and high-quality medical care to all Americans (Accreditation Council for

Graduate Medical Education [ACGME] 2019). Recognizing the importance of research and scholarly activities in training programs in the United States, ACGME requires residency training programs to include a research component in their curriculum. With this, residency programs must have the necessary resources (e.g., laboratory space and equipment, consultation services, faculty expertise and supervision, support personnel, and funding) to ensure that residents can meet their requirement for involvement in a scholarly activity project (ACGME 2019). It intends to equip the residents with basic principles of doing research and skills to apply medical/surgical evidence to patient care. However, despite mandating these scholarly requirements, studies show that residency programs often fall short of meeting the requirements and that there are factors which may affect research productivity (Fladie et al 2023).

To address challenges faced by residents trying to publish, several institutions, both in General Surgery and in other surgical disciplines, have created structured programs to improve the frequency and quality of residency writing and research (See Figure 1) (Forrester et al 2017, Penrose et al 2012, Kichler et al 2014, Robbins et al 2013). These programs have notable similarities such as the (1) development of a curriculum for training skills for effective research and publishing, (2) establishing expectations for scholastic productivity, (3) identifying a research coordinator responsible for maintaining collaboration between residents, faculty, and departments, and (4) ensuring publication timelines are achieved. Having a structured program can increase the chances of residents to publish quality and impactful research materials. National societies have also identified the need to help promote residency writing. For training programs or residents specifically interested in the potential for greater publishing, having dedicated research years or requirements for a set number of publications might be beneficial.

An effective writing and manuscript preparation program can bring residents and faculty into collaborative relationships based on mutual academic interests. Other studies evaluating strategies which promote publishing and scholastic writing will be beneficial to the training programs in terms of increasing the human resource in research and development in the surgical field.

Figure 1. Existing residency writing programs in surgery programs or surgical fields, United States.

Table 3 – Existing residency writing programs in surgery programs or surgical fields–United States.						
Authors	Year started	Specialty	Format	Degree of program director	Cost	Outcome
Robbins ⁷	2006	Orthopedics	Development of a research administrative infrastructure, curricula and requirements for publishing, and protected research time	Academic research coordinator (background in research and advanced degree in health education, public health, or a similar field)	\$19,000 per year for a research coordinator, \$16,000 for travel, and 213 hours of faculty reimbursement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase in resident grant funding from \$1875 per resident to \$4222 per resident - Four-fold increase in published manuscripts
Penrose ⁹	2008	Obstetrics and gynecology	"Dedicated research staff to facilitate and coordinate resident research projects, and support clinical faculty in research activities"	Postdoctoral researcher	Unknown	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More than doubling of research presentations among residents - Three- to four-fold increase in faculty submitted publications
Manring ⁸	2009	Orthopedics	Writing and research program for residents and faculty	PhD—Medical editor	"Salary range for a 'technical editor' falls between \$50,000 and \$60,000"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased number of papers with resident co-authors - Five-fold increase in overall department publications
Glew ¹²	2012	General surgery	Formal writing workshop for residents	PhD	Unknown	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "In the years before attending the workshop, four papers were published by these sixteen individuals; 1 year after the program they had published thirty-one papers in peer-reviewed journals"
Kichler ⁶	2012	General surgery	Formal writing curriculum and mentorship for residents	Two MD MPH faculty	Unknown	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mean number of scholarly activity items (presentations at meetings, submitted papers, and published articles) increased from 1 to 3.5 per year

Note: Adapted from (*Forrester et.al. 2017, p. 96*)

The situation about scholarly activity and research productivity among training programs in the country, particularly in Surgery, is very much the same. The Philippine College of Surgeons (PCS), the mother organization of all cutting specialties in the country and the Philippine Society of General Surgeons (PSGS), which make up most of the surgical specialists in the country, have noted the relevance of research in the training of surgeons, improvement of health outcomes and crafting of health policies. These organizations have provided teaching and learning activities as well as opportunities to promote research and its publication through workshops, webinars,

and various research fora and contests. In the General Surgery curriculum developed by the PSGS in 2017, research has been included as a learning outcome (PSGS Standardized Curriculum, 2017). However, it is only in the 2023 edition that a more detailed instructional design for research has been included (PSGS Outcomes-based Curriculum, 2023). Despite these improvements, there is still a lack of objective evaluation of research productivity among surgical programs in the country given the general perception that the research output of surgery residents rarely gets to be published.

As an organization of Filipino surgeons, there is a need to assess the distribution of research publications among residents-in-training under different training programs and identify factors related to research productivity. It will be useful for the surgical specialty organizations to recognize and analyze these factors so as not only to motivate the institutions and their trainees to engage in relevant research, but more importantly to improve the quality of their research output with concomitant improvement in the volume and utilization of published research in institutional and national policy setting.

Factors affecting research productivity

Research productivity may be influenced by several factors. Literature showed that various individual attributes and structural factors contribute to the increase or decrease of productivity. Babu and Singh (1998), in their analysis of factors influencing research productivity among scientists, revealed that out of 200 variables measured, 11 are deemed significant: “persistence, resource adequacy, access to literature, initiative, intelligence, creativity, learning capability, simulative leadership, concern for advancement, external orientation, and professional commitment.” Meanwhile,

Ramsden (1994) reported a study on academic productivity among Australian higher education and affirmed the observation that the average productivity is low, and the variation is high. It highlights that structural factor (e.g. organizational management of academic departments), combined with personal variables (e.g. intrinsic interest in the subject matter of one's discipline) help determine levels of productivity.

Dundar and Lewis (1998) looked into the impact of institutional factors and policies on doctorate-level research programs in the United States. The study population included only 30 program areas within four cluster fields (biological sciences, physical sciences and mathematics, social and behavioral sciences, and engineering) from 90 research classified universities. Based on review of the research literature and availability of data, several explanatory variables were included in their model for examination (See Figure 2). The authors assumed that research productivity as a dependent variable was largely measured by journal publications (between 1988 and 1992) and that this output was functionally related to those individual faculty and organizational attributes identified in Figure 2. Analysis shows that strong predictors of research productivity include a program and department size in terms of faculty number; being a private university, presence of "star" faculty; large percentage of faculty publishing, faculty with non-departmental financial research support; institution expenditure for libraries; high ratio of graduate students to faculty; percentage of graduate students who held research assistant posts. Moreover, faculty rank had a mixed effect on productivity.

Figure 2. Attributes associated with research productivity.

<i>Individual Attributes</i>
Innate abilities (i.e., IQ, personality, gender, and age)
Personal environmental influences (i.e., quality and culture of graduate training, and culture of employing department)
<i>Institutional and Departmental Attributes</i>
Institutional structure and leadership
Size of program and faculty
Control by private sector
Amount of university revenue
Availability of technology and computing facilities
Number of books and journals in library
Departmental culture and working conditions
Workload policies
Availability of leaves, travel, and institutional funds for research
Number of students on research support
Availability of "star" faculty
Availability of nongovernmental research funds

Sources: Past studies on research productivity.

Note: Adapted from (Dundar & Lewis, 1998, p. 614)

The findings from the study are important for US research universities for several reasons. It is useful in identifying other factors affecting research productivity. A more comprehensive approach is needed to identify factors affecting not only individual faculty but a department's research productivity as a whole. The interaction between individual and departmental factors which results in a productive research environment is still not well understood.

Bland et al (2005) developed a model which asserts that high research productivity is strongly associated with eight individual characteristics, fifteen institutional characteristics, and four leadership characteristics. (See Figure 3). This model has evolved through its application in several studies (Carole et al 2005). In the earlier version of the model, faculty research productivity is highest when a faculty member has specific individual qualities, works in an institution that is highly conducive to research, and is led by someone who possesses essential leadership qualities and uses an assertive-participatory management approach.

Figure 3. Description of individual, institutional, and leadership characteristics that facilitate research productivity.

List 1
Description of Individual, Institutional, and Leadership Characteristics That Facilitate Research Productivity

Individual	Institutional	Leadership
<p>1. Socialization: Understands the values, norms, expectations, and sanctions affecting established faculty (e.g., beneficence, academic freedom).</p> <p>2. Motivation: Driven to explore, understand, and follow one's own ideas, and to advance and contribute to society through innovation, discovery, and creative works.</p> <p>3. Content knowledge: Familiar—within one's research area—with all major published works, projects being conducted, differing theories, key researchers, and predominant funding sources.</p> <p>4. Basic and advanced research skills: Comfortable with statistics, study design, data collection methods, and advanced methods commonly used in one's area.</p> <p>5. Simultaneous projects: Engaged in multiple, concurrent projects, so as to buffer against disillusionment if one project stalls or fails.</p> <p>6. Orientation: Committed to both external activities (e.g., regional and national meetings, collaborating with colleagues) and activities within one's own organization (e.g., curriculum planning, institutional governance).</p> <p>7. Autonomy and commitment: Has academic freedom, plans one's own time and sets one's own goals, but is also committed to and plays a meaningful role within the larger organization.</p> <p>8. Work habits: Has established productive scholarly habits early on in one's career.</p>	<p>1. Recruitment and selection: Great effort is expended to recruit and hire members who have the training, goals, commitment, and socialization that match the institution.</p> <p>2. Clear coordinating goals: Visible, shared goals coordinate members' work.</p> <p>3. Research emphasis: Research has greater or equal priority than other goals.</p> <p>4. Culture: Members are bonded by shared, research-related values and practices, have a safe home for testing new ideas.</p> <p>5. Positive group climate: The climate is characterized by high morale, a spirit of innovation, dedication to work, receptivity to new ideas, frequent interactions, high degree of cooperation, low member turnover, good leader/member relationships, and open discussion of disagreements.</p> <p>6. Mentoring: Beginning and midlevel members are assisted by and collaborate with established scholars.</p> <p>7. Communication with professional network: Members have a vibrant network of colleagues with whom they have frequent and substantive (not merely social) research communication, both impromptu and formal, in and outside of the institution.</p> <p>8. Resources: Members have access to sufficient resources such as funding, facilities, and especially humans (e.g., local peers for support, research assistants, technical consultants).</p> <p>9. Sufficient work time: Members have significant periods of uninterrupted time to devote to scholarly activities.</p> <p>10. Size/experience/expertise: Members offer different perspectives by virtue of differences in their degree levels, approaches to problems, and varying discipline backgrounds; the group is stable, and its size is at or above a "critical mass."</p> <p>11. Communication: Clear and multiple forms of communication such that all members feel informed.</p> <p>12. Rewards: Research is rewarded equitably and in accordance with defined benchmarks of achievement; potential rewards include money, promotion, recognition, and new responsibilities.</p> <p>13. Brokered opportunities: Professional development opportunities are routinely and proactively offered to members to assure their continued growth and vitality.</p> <p>14. Decentralized organization: Governance structures are flat and decentralized where participation of members is expected.</p> <p>15. Assertive participative governance: Clear and common goals, assertive and participative leadership where active participation of members is expected, and effective feedback systems are utilized.</p>	<p>1. Scholar: Highly regarded as a scholar; serves as a sponsor, mentor, and peer model for other group members.</p> <p>2. Research oriented: Possesses a "research orientation"; has internalized the group's research-centered mission.</p> <p>3. Capably fulfills all critical leadership roles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Manager of people and resources ● Fund-raiser ● Group advocate ● Keeps the group's mission and shared goals visible to all members ● Attends to the many individual and institutional features that facilitate research productivity <p>4. Participative leader:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Uses an assertive, participative style of leadership ● Holds frequent meetings with clear objectives ● Creates formal mechanisms and sets expectations for all members to contribute to decision making ● Makes high-quality information readily available to the group ● Vests ownership of projects with members and values their ideas

Note: Adapted from (Bland et. al. 2005, p. 228)

Figure 4. Model of research productivity.

Note: Adapted from (Bland et al. 2005, p. 227)

Meanwhile, a study among Canadian surgical specialties (Wang et al 2021) noted the variability in research productivity wherein cardiac surgery and neurosurgery were found to be productive, whereas vascular surgery and plastic surgery are less productive than other surgical disciplines. Further, obtaining a research-oriented graduate degree, being a part of a clinical group, and the presence of a training program were linked with higher productivity.

While national governments in Asia also expect universities to be effective in teaching and research, the same concern on low levels of research outcomes has been observed. Obstructions to research productivity must be resolved by universities to increase the research output of their academic staff. One study conducted in a

public university in Thailand (Lertputtarak 2008) tried to focus on the factors that have an influence on the low research productivity of academic lecturers in the institution. It shows that essential factors (i.e., career development factors such as attitude, skills, experience, academic origin, tenure status, and highest degree) potentially contribute to higher quality and quantity research outcomes.

A study by Quimbo and Sulabo (2014) analyzed the productivity of 300 faculty members from five state universities as a response to the Commission on Higher Education's development plan of enhancing research culture in higher education institutions. Among the factors which turned out to be important predictors of research productivity and research self-efficacy include educational attainment, research benefits and incentive system.

In the University of Santo Tomas (UST) Faculty of Medicine and Surgery (FMS), the course on clinical epidemiology was introduced as part of the curriculum in 2008 to improve the medical students' understanding of evidence-based medicine (EBM) and research methods to subsequently improve the institution's research productivity. The course involves lectures and group activities on four years of basic medical education. Students were tasked to develop research proposals during their first year of study and then implement them in their second and third year in the program. Actual research paper writing and research presentation were done before graduation. In relation to this, a student-led study (Arada et al 2022) found that while students value EBM, they are less inclined in conducting research due to their busy schedule as well as other intrinsic factors (e.g., limited knowledge of statistics). Hospitals should also create avenues to support the research endeavors of their physicians.

Finally, a structured review by Laupland et al (2021) on graduate medical education trainee research productivity revealed that prior research experience, later

years of training, male gender, and pursuit of a postgraduate degree are linked with higher research productivity. As such, publication of trainees was associated with higher-ranking mentors, publication productivity and supportive academic environments.

Barriers to research productivity

While there are factors which positively influence research productivity, there are also studies which discuss those which negatively impact productivity in doing scholarly work (Sciarretta et al 2019; Fournier et al 2018; The Canadian Plastic Surgery Research Collaborative [CPSRC] 2017; David et al 2020; and Winter et al 2021). Generally, it indicates that lack of dedicated time, necessary resources and support are key barriers to research productivity among residents.

A survey (Sciarretta et al 2019) on the perspectives of residents on their research program revealed that delays in research work were due to a lack of structured curriculum (50%), technical support (45.8%), research experience (37.5%), and interest (33%).

Meanwhile, a study specific among Otorhinolaryngology trainees (Fournier et al 2018) found out that the three most frequent obstacles to successfully completing their research projects include: dedicated time (64%), insufficient financial resources (55%) and lack of education in research (45%). Similarly, a study among plastic surgery trainees in Canada (CPSRC 2017) reported that the top three perceived barriers to conducting research were lack of time (83%), insufficient access to research supervisors and mentors (42%) and the research ethics process (38%). Another study among radiology trainees showed the same barriers such as time constraints, lack of interest, inadequate mentorship, and limited research training

(Winter et al 2021). Finally, Gangwish et al (2020) indicated the attitude of faculty members towards residents' scholarly activity as a key barrier.

Research program, research curriculum or dedicated research time as facilitators of research productivity

To improve research interest and participation of residents, a variety of guidelines and strategies particularly the implementation of a research curriculum have been used in a variety of specialties, including General Surgery (Lucas et al 2021; Gupta et al 2021; Schwartz et al 2022). A study by Lucas et al (2021) reported the development of a research curriculum with milestones, a long-term outcome and sustainability, and its impact on the overall departmental research culture— which was associated with improved long-term research productivity. This allowed residents to work closely with faculty and medical students leading to more collaborations, resulting in an enhanced scholarly environment. In another study by Gupta et al (2021), a department wide research curriculum and infrastructure was created to encourage academic collaboration and productivity among trainees who engage in different types of research. In this setting, surgery residents who were on dedicated research time (DRT) were primarily involved, expanded later on to include trainees and faculty at all levels of the institution. Guest lecturers from various institutions were accommodated through virtual meeting platforms. Research meetings, didactics, and the guest-lecture series were attended by medical students, residents, and clinical and research faculty from the Department of Surgery. They were given access to shared resources and were encouraged to share their own work. This initiative may be considered a low-cost, feasible, and accessible way to improve academic productivity and enhance the training of surgeon-scientists.

There are several studies which attest that having a dedicated research time or research program within the overall training curriculum of residents could help improve research output outcomes. Different programs have a different term for it such as a multifaceted research engagement program (William et al 2020), a formal research program within residency (Hsieh et al 2014), a dedicated quarterly research meeting (Holoyda et al 2019); clinical research program (Merwin, Fornari & Lane 2014); Surgical Research Methodology Program (Huynh et al 2021; Foorkhyar et al 2014); and Structured Research Rotations (Pernar et al 2022). Despite this, they all have the advantage of helping residents understand research and improve their scholarly activity.

According to Frankel (2020) their research engagement program has four pillars: research requirement, structured research curriculum, infrastructure to support residents' research, and an annual resident research day to highlight trainees' work. Implementation of this multifaceted research engagement program was associated with a significant increase in manuscripts published by General Surgery residents, including clinical track residents. Holoyda et al (2019) observed the need for a supportive environment and strong mentorship process. It is their strong mentor relationships during plastic surgery residency which has been associated with an improved publication during residency as well as eventual academic career. Furthermore, the dedicated research time allowed for regular updates on their ongoing research, discussion of new projects and identification of stalled projects that could motivate residents to work toward publication. Financial support and funding are also necessary to produce research. Academic development time is particularly challenging to support because the residents are free of clinical responsibility during this time.

The official inception of a formalized program in an Orthopedic Surgery Department (Merwin et al 2014) noted that structured tools, an experienced clinical research “champion” and commitment from departmental leadership were effective in transforming the focus of a clinical department into an evolving clinical research program, with demonstrable outcomes. Huynh et al (2021), in their study, demonstrated the positive effect of integrating research into the medical curriculum by way of an 8-week mentored surgical research program. In this program, a student was paired with a faculty mentor on an assigned research project. Weekly updates are given during faculty - led work in progress meetings. Lectures, basic research skills and conferences for early clinical exposure were also included. The study showed that the program helped the students submit abstracts to a national meeting with 5 accepted for oral presentation. An integrated research program within the medical school curriculum can provide students with the basic skills to foster their academic achievement and later on help them become successful in their careers.

Another version of a Surgical Research Methodology program (Farrokyar et al 2014) was introduced in a university in Canada. To promote the research profiles and EBM practice of their surgical residents, a formal 2-year educational research curriculum was embedded within the surgical residency-protected teaching time of the Surgical Foundations (SF) curriculum. A cohort study was then done to assess whether the implementation of the formal SRM Program led to an improvement in the surgical residents’ research productivity and performance compared with the preceding informal Research Seminar Series (RSS). In the SRM Program, the curriculum in Year-1 consisted of 12 teaching sessions on the principles of clinical epidemiology and biostatistics, whereas the focus in Year-2 was on the design, conduct, and presentation of a research project. The RSS consisted of 8 research

methodology sessions repeated annually for 2 years along with the design, conduct, and presentation of a research project. Research productivity was measured as the number of peer-reviewed publications and the generation of studies with higher levels of evidence. This SRM Program is instrumental in improving the residents' research productivity. The study found that residents who received a structured education of epidemiology and biostatistics performed significantly better on all metrics in the evaluation of research productivity and performance.

Pernar et al (2022) described structured research rotations or four weeks of research blocks wherein research projects are developed and prepared in advance to maximize productivity during the research rotation. Through this approach, they were able to increase resident engagement in a variety of research activities without extending training time. Stevenson et al. (2017) concluded in their study that residency programs offering protected research time, established research criteria, and providing a specialized research track increased residency scholarly activity, including overall number of publications.

Other Factors Affecting Research Productivity

Other factors which can promote research productivity as shown in various studies include: institution of a mandatory research requirement consisting of different components (such as a curriculum comprised of monthly research meetings and lectures, assigned faculty to act as research mentors, an online repository of research projects and ideas, statistical support, and a faculty member appointed Director of Research) (Papasavas et al 2013); successful completion of graduate degree and prior publication experience of the trainee (Lee et al 2023); education and funding support (Lampman et al 2003); faculty mentoring and establishment of research teams

(Lampman et al 2003; Lohr et al 2006); and strategic recruitment of faculty members who were research scientists.

Ensuring Research Productivity in training programs

While academic research has been considered an integral part of General Surgery training and despite the research curriculum requirements of the ACGME for US based training programs and by the PSGS locally, there is still a perceived low level of research productivity among these programs and the trainees. A review of the literature on factors influencing research productivity revealed feasible strategies which may be adapted by the programs to improve and ensure scholarly activity by trainees to maximize the benefits, not only to the individual but also to the program.

The study by Brochu et al (2018) sought to identify research opportunities, structure, and academic outputs during General Surgery residency in the US by doing a web-based review. Among 242 General Surgery trainees, the study noted that there is much variability in research structure, process, and outcomes. The authors suggest that programs should consider the opportunity to offer varied types of research, with the potential to pursue an advanced degree. In addition, guidelines should be developed regarding resident research structure, process, and outcomes.

Synthesis

Several studies present various individual attributes and structural factors which contribute to the increase or decrease of productivity. Babu and Singh (1998), in their analysis of factors influencing research productivity among scientists, revealed that out of 200 variables measured, 11 are deemed significant: persistence, resource adequacy, access to literature, initiative, intelligence, creativity, learning capability,

simulative leadership, concern for advancement, external orientation, and professional commitment.

Bland et al (2005) developed a model asserting that high research productivity is strongly associated with eight individual characteristics, fifteen institutional characteristics, and four leadership characteristics. This model has evolved through its application in several studies (Carole et al 2005). In the earlier version of the model, faculty research productivity is highest when a faculty member has specific individual qualities, works in an institution that is highly conducive to research, and is led by someone who possesses essential leadership qualities and uses an assertive–participatory management approach. There are also several studies which attest that having a dedicated research time or research program within the overall training curriculum of residents can help improve the research output. (William et al 2020; Hsieh et al 2014; Holoyda et al 2019; Merwin, Fornari & Lane 2014; Huynh et al 2021; Foorkhyar et al 2014; and Pernar et al 2022).

Based on these published studies, we seek to evaluate how these factors affect the research productivity of General Surgery programs in our setting.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 5. Conceptual Framework

Operational Definition

1. Research productivity will be defined as follows:

- a. Personal research productivity can be measured by the number of research papers published during training and the number of research outputs presented in a forum/contest
- b. Institutional research productivity refers to the compliance of the training program to the research requirements set by their society or institution and be measured based on the:

1. Number of research papers completed per training year.
2. Percentage of research presented in a forum per training year,
and
3. Percentage of research output published per year

2. Adaptive outcomes-based Research Curriculum

Curriculum which emphasizes learning outcomes related to capacity to do research and can be adjusted according to the needs of the trainee and the program.

3. Personal factors include sociodemographic variables like age, sex, year level of training, pre-medical course (science or non-science related), experience in doing research and publication prior to residency training and values which may include motivational values (persistence, resource adequacy, access to literature, initiative, intelligence, creativity, learning capability, simulative leadership, concern for advancement, external orientation, and professional commitment).

4. Institutional factors refer to having or following a research agenda, research policy on dedicated time, trainings, financial support, research mentor, rewards & incentives; having an accredited IRB and pursuing collaborative research

5. Junior level resident – first year in training

6. Intermediate level resident – second and third year in training
7. Senior level resident – fourth and fifth year in training

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This is a mixed method research using a sequential exploratory approach which involves a quantitative study design (analytical cross section) initially and followed by a qualitative approach using FGD.

Sampling Technique

The target population are General Surgery residents and representative research coordinator consultants from the different accredited General Surgery Training programs in the Philippines which may or may not have concomitant Surgical Specialty programs such as Neurosurgery, Orthopedic Surgery, Otorhinolaryngology, Pediatric Surgery, Plastic & Reconstructive Surgery, Thoracic & Cardiovascular Surgery, and Urology.

Sample size computation using Open epi was applied to get 95% confidence with a power of 80% (See Appendix A and B). For generalizability of study results, the different training programs' resident population was the sampling frame and all trainees were included. simple random sampling for the General Surgery residents (according to year level of training) was planned, however majority of the General Surgery residents participated in the study (1014/1072).

For the consultant or research coordinator group, the set inclusion criteria include being from an accredited General Surgery training program from a tertiary medical institution, with at least two years as a consultant staff of the department and

a member of the Training or research committee. Simple random sampling was done for the consultant group.

Setting

The study involves General Surgery training institutions with the residents under an accredited training program of PSGS and the consultant staff who are involved as research coordinators, implementing the surgical curriculum, and monitoring the achievement of learning outcomes, including research output.

Data Collection

After securing an IRB review and approval, permission was sought from the current PSGS board to conduct the study among the residents and consultant research coordinators. A copy of the research protocol was sent for their review and approval.

After approval, the content of the data collection form was transferred into two different google forms, one for the residents and another for the consultants. Data collection for the residents was arranged during a national comprehensive exam to ensure adequacy of filled up forms. Meanwhile, data collection form for consultants was sent to them via email.

For the FGD, random sampling was done among training officers or research coordinators from the 71 regular accredited programs according to the type of institution they belong to. Surgical residents who participated in the survey were randomly chosen as well. Each FGD consisted of 10 participants. Participants were asked further about the responses gathered from the questionnaire to determine the

underlying reason for the responses and provide a more in-depth explanation of their own perspectives and experiences.

Research Instrument

There were two survey forms utilized in the data collection process: one for the General Surgery resident to determine the personal factors and the other one for the consultant research coordinator to identify the institutional factors affecting research productivity in General Surgery training programs.

For the trainee survey form, it comprised sociodemographic factors such as age, gender, year level of training and the category of their training institution. Factors which may have an effect on their current research productivity such as their research background: pre-medical course, past experience in research and publication, attitude towards research, were also included. Also included were questions about their research productivity like the number of times they have presented research in a forum and published their research per training year. The last set of questions covered what they think about research productivity, reasons why it is limited, and also possible strategies to improve on it (See Appendix C).

For the consultant survey form, it included sociodemographic factors such as their age, gender and type of training institution, the research productivity of their department in terms of percentage of research presented/ or published per year and the more important institutional factors affecting research productivity such as: research policies, research program with an agenda, availability and quality of research mentors, regular workshops; support for research such as incentives, budget presence of an IRB; and their participation in collaborative research (See Appendix D). Both questionnaires underwent review for clarity of the questions and the choices.

For the FGD, questions were made after reviewing the results of the survey. The purpose of the FGD was to help elucidate and expound on the responses that were obtained from the survey forms.

Plan for Data analysis

Descriptive statistics was used to present the socio-demographic characteristics of the study respondents. The personal and institutional factors were reported as frequency distribution.

ANOVA was used to compare the means of two or more independent groups to determine if there is statistical evidence that the associated populations' means are significantly different.

Regression analysis and Chi squared test was done to determine association of factors and the different measures of research productivity.

For the FGD, qualitative analysis was done using data analysis software MaxQDA. Accordingly, thematic analysis was employed to look into patterns among the experiences of training officers, research coordinators, and surgical residents relative to their individual research productivity. A combination of close coding and in-vivo coding was utilized in analyzing the FGDs. Close coding pertains to the process of using concepts from the FGD guide questions to code the responses of the participants, while in-vivo coding involves using concepts based on the actual responses only. The thematic analysis of the respondents focuses on aspects such as significance of research in the General Surgery program, strategies and/or resources available, barriers and motivations to do research, among others.

Data Management

The primary investigator will be responsible to keep the data collected from the conduct of the study for a period of five years. There is a planned follow up study to determine if there would be an improvement on research productivity after strategies have been implemented.

Ethical Considerations

Permission from PSGS to conduct the study among the different programs was obtained after getting an IRB approval. The list of the General Surgery residents all over the Philippines as well as the Training Officers or research coordinators was then obtained from PSGS. Informed consent was included in the Google form sent to the target participants by email. Those who agreed to participate proceeded to answer the survey forms. (See Appendix E).

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sociodemographic Characteristics

From the survey questionnaires and FGDs conducted, the research productivity of General Surgery residents from accredited five-year training programs in the country has been evaluated. A total of 1014 (94.6%) General Surgery residents out of a total of 1072 registered under the PSGS and 58 (81.7%) consultant research coordinators from 71 accredited training programs participated in the quantitative part of the study.

The sociodemographic profile of General Surgery residents from the various training programs in the Philippines is shown in Table 1. Most of the participants are within the age range of 30-35 years ($n= 585, 57.69\%$). In terms of sex distribution, there are more male participants compared to female participants (3:2 ratio). Most of the residents belong to DOH-affiliated training institutions (37%) while the least are local government hospitals (16.6%). This may be due to the higher number of salaried or plantilla (i.e., permanent) items available in DOH hospitals compared to the private and local government hospitals.

In terms of current year level of training, most of the participants are in level III based on the PSGS curriculum (senior or year 4 and 5), accounting for 38.3%; while 36% belong to level II (intermediate or year 2 and 3) and 24.2 % are in level I or junior year. Although the General Surgery program is only for 5 years, there were 15 respondents (1.5%) who indicated that they are in year level VI and VII.

For the pre-medical courses, ninety seven percent of the participants are from science-related courses, and only three percent are from non-science related courses.

This finding is expected since these courses covers subjects which prepare students for the study of Medicine in addition to preparing them to take the National Medical Admission Test.

Table 1

Summary of the Sociodemographic Characteristics of General Surgery Trainees

Range of Age	N = 1014	% of total
24-29	349	34.4%
30-35	585	57.7%
36-40	63	6.2%
41-45	15	1.5%
46-50	1	0.1 %
51-55	1	0.1 %
Sex Distribution		
Male	579	57.1%
Female	435	42.9%
Training Institution		
Academic (University hospital)	199	19.6%
DOH affiliated	375	37.0%
Local Government Hospital	168	16.6%
Private Hospital	272	26.8%
Year Level of Training		
I	245	24.2%
II	174	17.2%
III	191	18.8%
IV	194	19.1 %
V	195	19.2%
VI, VII	15	1.48%

Pre-Medical Course		
Science related (Bio, Zoo, Psych, Nursing, Med Tech, etc.)	987	97.34%
Non-Science Related	27	2.66%

For the training coordinator, their socio demographic profile is shown in Table 2. Most of the participants are in the age range of 41-50 years (n=26), while the least are those who are >60 years old (n=6). In terms of sex distribution, there are more males compared to females (3:1). For the training institution, most of the participants belong to DOH-affiliated institutions, 39.7% (23/58) while only a few are from academic (university hospital) and local government hospitals accounting for 15.5% each. More than half of the participants (79%) belong to a training institution which has other training programs in Surgery aside from General Surgery. This may have an impact on the variety of research these training institutions have.

Table 2

Summary of the Sociodemographic Characteristics of Training Coordinators

Age Range	N = 58	% of total
30-40	15	25.9%
41-50	26	44.8%
51-60	11	19.0%
>60	6	10.3%
Sex		
Female	16	27.6%
Male	42	72.4%
Training Institution		
Academic (University hospital)	9	15.5%
DOH affiliated	23	39.7%

Local Government Hospital	9	15.5%
Private	17	29.3%

Personal Factors Affecting Research Productivity

The trainees' overall attitude towards research was positive, with 610/1014 (60.16%) respondents who believe that research during training is essential. There were 177 (17.46%) respondents who said that research helps improve patient care and could also improve their chances for fellowship. However, there were 96 (9.47%) respondents who thought that research is just a requirement for graduation and 32 (3.16%) respondents who have a negative attitude towards research considering it as a waste of time and effort (See Table 3). These were further explored during the FGD with residents.

Table 3.

Trainees' Thoughts about Research during Training

Trainees thinking about research during training	N = 1014	% of total
Essential	610	60.16%
Helps improve patient care after training or getting into fellowship	177	17.46%
Provide opportunities	91	8.97%
Promotes self-efficacy	15	1.48%
Improves chances of being employed	8	0.79%
Rewarding	4	0.4%
Just need to complete it for promotion/graduation	96	9.47 %
Waste of time and effort	30	2.96%
Have ideas but don't have the time	1	0.6%

Trainees thinking about research during training	N = 1014	% of total
Don't research. I want only to develop my skills	1	0.1 %

Although the majority (74.7%) had research subjects during their undergraduate years, only 50.5% had publications during their pre- Medicine and Medicine proper years. (See Table 4).

Table 4

Summary of Pre–Training Research Exposure and Experience of the General Surgery Residents

Trainees who have research subjects during pre-med or med	N = 1014	% of total
With research subject	757	74.7%
No research subject	257	25.3%
Publications during pre-med or med		
With publications	512	50.5%
No publications	502	49.5%

As shown in Table 5, surgical trainees have multiple sources for their research topics, with the top two sources coming from the cases they encountered (140 responses) and from their research adviser (129).

Residents' encounter with research during training is not only in the aspect of creating a scientific article. They are also trained to utilize scientific publications to support evidence-based patient management. Journal clubs with critical appraisal of the literature are scheduled regularly and ideally, knowledge gaps identified during this academic exercise, aside from the course of patient management, could be explored

as a relevant topic for their research activity. Furthermore, the role of surgical consultants, who have experience in managing various surgical conditions in the research activity of residents is very essential. Surgical trainees would naturally be curious and could easily get interested in any case they would encounter not knowing that much research has already been done on that topic. It is the consultant who can guide them in developing plausible, feasible and relevant research questions on topics that have not yet been studied and considered a pressing knowledge gap. Consultants with their connections not only with co-surgeons but with other specialist in the field of medicine and in their participation in professional organizations could also leverage research within the institution into multispecialty, multi-institutional research with much improved validity and generalizability.

Table 5

Source of Research Ideas of Trainees

Source of research ideas of Trainees	N = 1014	% of total
Cases Encountered	140	13.8%
Research adviser	129	12.7%
Scientific journals	41	4.0%
Curiosity	27	2.7 %
Books	4	0.4%
More than 1 source	673	66.4%

Research productivity measures of surgical trainees

Most of the trainees engage in at least one research as a primary investigator (n=796, 78.5%), and about 131 (12.9%) are involved in various research. There were 87 (8.6%) residents with no research involvement at the time of the data collection.

With regards to being a co-investigator, most of the trainees engage in at least one research as a co-investigator (n=758, 74.8%), and 141 (13.9%) are not currently involved as co-investigator in another research.

Based on the recommendation from PSGS, the residents should have done a case report and another scientific paper (either descriptive or analytical quantitative research, or qualitative if they decide to) before they graduate from the program for a total of two scientific papers. Considering this directive from PSGS, the number of residents with at least one research as a primary investigator relative to the time of data collection is acceptable since it is expected that at this time, second year to fifth year residents already have at least one research. The first-year residents are usually the ones who would experience a delay in writing their research proposal and probably account for the 8.6% of residents with no research yet.

In some institutions, research collaborations between senior and junior residents are required to ensure continuity of the study if ever the senior would graduate and the research still needs to be continued to improve sample size compliance, for future studies emanating from that research and to pursue its publication. This practice by some institutions could be considered as a factor which can promote research productivity ensuring that the works gets to be published, utilized and be a source of future research.

Although there seems to be an adequate amount of research being conducted by the residents, there is a need to increase the proportion of research which gets to be presented in a forum and published eventually. Although most of the General Surgery trainees had at least one presentation in a research forum (47.5%) there are also many residents who have not experienced presenting their research in a public forum. With regards to publication, a greater percentage of the residents-in-training

has no published research during the time of data collection (68.7%). There were only 299 (29.5%) with at least one scientific publication (Table 6).

The practice of holding an annual departmental or institutional scientific research forum is not uniformly done in the General surgery research programs, hence not all residents get the chance to present their work. This practice is usually observed in academic institutions and DOH affiliated hospitals because they have the support system (a research unit, budget, access to specialist who can function as judges) to carry out the research presentation. Starting 2023, the PSGS has started to include opportunities for research presentation for the residents. Aside from encouraging chapter research contests, a free paper and poster session have been included in the Annual PSGS Surgical Forum. The different training programs are also encouraged to join international scientific forum with call for abstract submission. The effect of this initiative on research productivity may be observed in the coming years.

Table 6

Summary of research productivity measures of the GS residents

Number of research currently involved in as primary investigator	N = 1014	% of total
None	87	8.6%
One	796	78.5%
More than 1	131	12.9%
Number of research currently involved in as co-investigator		
None	141	13.9%
One	758	74.8%
Two	79	7.8%
More than 2	36	3.6%

Number of times presented research in a forum during residency		
None	416	41.0%
Once	482	47.5%
Twice	88	8.7%
More than twice	28	2.76%

Number of research published during training		
None	697	68.7%
One	299	29.5%
Two	13	1.3%
More than two	5	0.5%

Using ANOVA, we sought to determine if personal factors such as level of training, type of program and prior research exposures are associated with research productivity.

Year level of Training Institution and research productivity

A Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to assess the association between the year level of training and the frequency of research presentations in a forum. The test revealed a statistically significant difference among groups ($\chi^2(6) = 81.292, p < 0.001, \epsilon^2 = 0.080$), indicating a moderate effect (See Appendix F).

Post hoc pairwise comparisons using the Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner procedure were conducted to determine specific group differences. The results indicate the following significant differences with no significant differences observed between certain pairs of groups (see details in the results) (See Appendix G).

1. Group III vs. Group I ($W=-7.280, p<0.001$)
2. Group I vs. Group II ($W=6.205, p<0.001$)
3. Group I vs. Group IV ($W=10.100, p<0.001$)
4. Group I vs. Group V ($W=10.748, p<0.001$)
5. Group II vs. Group V ($W=4.368, p=0.033$)

These findings suggest that the frequency of research presentations in a forum varies significantly among the year level of training (junior versus intermediate and senior level). The higher the level of training, the higher the chance of presenting in a research forum.

A Kruskal-Wallis test was also conducted to examine the association between the year level of training and the number of publications during training. The results revealed a statistically significant difference among groups ($\chi^2(6) = 37.548, p<0.001, \epsilon^2=0.037$), demonstrating a small effect (See Appendix H).

Post hoc pairwise comparisons using the Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner procedure were conducted to explore specific group differences. The results indicate the following significant differences:

1. Group I vs. Group IV ($W=5.562, p=0.002$)
2. Group I vs. Group V ($W=7.715, p<0.001$)
3. Group II vs. Group V ($W=4.379, p=0.032$)

No significant differences were observed between certain pairs of groups (see details in the results) (See Appendix I).

These findings suggest that the frequency of publishing during training varies significantly among the trainee groups, specifically between the junior and senior level.

Further exploration of the pairwise differences provide insight into specific group distinctions.

The analysis showed that higher level residents have more experience in research presentation and publication. Although this may be expected because of the longer time senior residents have been in the program, junior level residents should not be discouraged to present and publish their work. There could be a bias in effect and seniors have been stereotypically assigned to join research presentations because of their proficiency in the topic and relatively better self-confidence than the juniors. There is a need to move beyond this status quo and encourage junior level residents to publish their work. This outcome is more achievable in the coming years with the present directive from PSGS that juniors should complete a case report by second year level. In addition, continuing education activities with workshops to help capacitate the residents in presenting their work in a public forum as well as in publication should be supported and held regularly.

Category of Training Institution and research productivity

Difference in research productivity (number of times presented research in a forum) according to the category of the training institution.

To investigate the association between different types of training institutions and the frequency of trainees presenting their research in a forum, the Kruskal-Wallis test was also performed. The results indicated a statistically significant difference among the groups ($\chi^2(3) = 10.613$, $p = 0.014$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.010$), suggesting a small effect. (See Appendix J)

Post hoc pairwise comparisons using the Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner procedure were performed to explore specific group differences in the frequency of research presentations. The results are as follows:

1. **Academic (University hospital) vs. Private:** $W=3.994, p=0.025$

- A significant difference was found, indicating that trainees from academic (University hospital) and private institutions differ in the frequency of presenting their research in a forum.

2. **DOH affiliated vs. Private:** $W=3.582, p=0.055$

- A marginally significant difference suggests that trainees from DOH affiliated and private institutions may differ in their presentation frequency.

No significant differences were observed in the presentation frequency between other pairs of training institutions (see details in the results) (See Appendix K).

These findings suggest that the frequency of presenting their research in a forum varies significantly among different types of training institutions, with specific differences identified between trainees from academic (University hospital) and private institutions.

Difference in research productivity (frequency of publication) according to the category of the training institution

To determine the association between different types of training institutions and the frequency of submitting publications during General Surgery training, the Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted. The results did not reveal a statistically significant

difference among the groups ($\chi^2(3) = 4.481, p = 0.214, \epsilon^2 = 0.004$), suggesting **a lack of evidence for** a significant effect (See Appendix L)

Post hoc pairwise comparisons using the Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner procedure were performed to examine specific group differences in the frequency of publishing during training. The results are as follows:

1. **Academic (University hospital) vs. Private:** $W = 2.578, p = 0.263$

- No significant difference was found, indicating similar frequencies of trainees publishing during training between academic (University hospital) and private institutions.

2. **DOH affiliated vs. Private:** $W = 1.868, p = 0.550$

- No significant difference was found, suggesting that trainees from DOH affiliated and private institutions have similar frequencies of publishing during training.

No significant differences were observed in the frequency of publishing during training between other pairs of training institutions (see details in the results) (See Appendix M). These findings suggest that there is no significant variation in the frequency of trainees publishing during training among different types of training institutions.

The analysis on the association between the category of the training institution and research productivity showed that the residents from the academic institutions and DOH affiliated hospitals have better research presentation experience compared to their counterparts from the private hospital and LGU. In terms of publications, there is no difference among the training programs. This finding can be explained by the availability of an annual research forum being held in the “bigger” institutions. The

office of Professional Education, Training, and Research of DOH hospitals and the corresponding Training and research Office of academic institutions have historically held these scientific colloquia because these are part of their targets or deliverables which they have set in their respective operational plan and anchored on their institution's key result areas. They have the motivation to attain these since these form part of their performance evaluation and has corresponding incentive and reward which comes in the form of a budget to support research related activities. The local government unit and private hospitals may benchmark with the other institutions to determine how they too can organize such research forum and provide opportunities for their trainees to present their work.

In the aspect of research publication, we can see clearly that there is uniformly low research publication among the programs. There is a need to look into this situation of low research productivity and determine what barriers need to be corrected and which factors are still needed to promote more publications.

Research Exposures in Med School and Research productivity

A Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to examine the association between having a research subject in Med school and the number of times they presented their research in a forum. The results did not indicate a statistically significant difference between the two groups ($\chi^2(1) = 0.014$, $p=0.907$), suggesting **no evidence for a significant effect.** (See Appendix N)

Similarly, a Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to examine potential differences among groups in terms of the frequency of trainees' publication. The results revealed a non-significant effect ($\chi^2(1) = 0.003$, $p=0.957$), indicating no statistically significant

variation in publishing frequency among the groups who had a research subject in med school and those who did not have. (See Appendix O)

A Kruskal-Wallis test was also conducted to examine potential differences among those who had experience in publication during pre- residency years and those who did not have publications in terms of the frequency of trainees' presentation in a research forum. The results showed a non-significant effect ($\chi^2(1) = 2.380, p = 0.123$), suggesting that there is no statistically significant variation in the frequency of presenting research among the groups. (See Appendix P)

Moreover, a Kruskal-Wallis test was also conducted to determine potential differences among groups (with and without publication during pre-residency years) and the frequency of publications during residency training. The results revealed a statistically significant effect ($\chi^2(1) = 10.236, p = 0.001, \epsilon^2 = 0.010$), indicating that there is a significant variation in the frequency of publishing during training among the groups. (See Appendix Q). This finding shows that residents who had previous experience in publication prior to their residency training tend to have more publications compared to their counterparts. This observation is shared by a study by Kohlert et al, 2017, which showed that residents who had at least one publication before residency had six times more probability of publishing during residency compared to those who had none. However, the authors cannot explain the underlying reason for this finding and instead suggested to look deeper on the effect of the research environment, personal variables and publication variables which could have affected the research productivity of the trainees in this study. Kohlert et al suggested to use pre residency publication as a criterion for admission to the program.

This observation can be used to test a strategy of encouraging research publications even at the preparatory level and Medicine proper. Likewise, these

residents with prior research publications may be assigned to a key role by the research committee of the institution such as sharing their experience in publication with the co-residents during their research consultation hour or by giving tips on the publication process.

Barriers to Research productivity from the surgical trainees' perspective

Tables 7, 8 and 9 present the various reasons pointed out as a cause for limited research productivity in General Surgery training programs. Lack of time emerged as the most common reason given by more than half of the respondents as the main factor affecting the conduct of research, its presentation and publication. They reasoned out that there is no dedicated time for research within the training period and most of their time is allotted mainly in conducting clinical work. The focus of surgical programs is more on patient management and other hospital activities that would include performing surgeries, doing outpatient consultations and procedures, ward rounds, hospital conferences and other extracurricular activities. This would leave limited time to accomplish research related activities such as subject recruitment, data collection, manuscript writing and complying with the publication process. With regards to publication, residents lack the time to finish and publish their research before graduation. Currently, there are no policies yet requiring training programs to provide dedicated time for research within a training year. This is an important variable to look at if we want to see an improvement in research productivity. Looking at the five-year General Surgery curriculum, certain stages for research completion may be allotted a cumulative time period. For example, the first-year resident tasked to complete a case report by first year would need to undergo a simple research ethics workshop (24 hours); application for IRB review (24 hours), writing the case report with review of

literature (40 hours). This totals to 88 hours which the resident may apply for a leave from his clinical work to attend to his research related task. The same can be done for all residents and it would be the role of the training officer or research coordinator to coordinate these planned leaves. Just as support for the resident's research aspirations are being provided, they would have the responsibility to comply with the timeline set and failure to do so may lead to corresponding sanction or loss of privileged time. For the more complex research output such as analytical studies, a corresponding amount of time, as long as reasonable and feasible may be provided. A support system may also be put in place to augment this needed time for research such as a research assistant who can help the residents' complete documentations related to the IRB application process and other. This however entails a budget which not all institutions may be able to provide.

A significant percentage of the respondents considered the tedious IRB process (12.13%) as a barrier to research productivity. There is an existing joint DOST, DOH, CHED and UPM Memorandum Order 001 series of 2012 that requires "all human health research to undergo ethical review and clearance to ensure the safety, dignity and well-being of research participants". Although this regulation adds a significant amount of time before a human health research can be initiated (from one to three months and even about half a year to comply with), this is a compulsory step in the conduct of research which cannot be avoided, unless the organization will allow the residents to just accomplish a Systematic Review and/or Meta-analysis which are both exempted from ethical review. In the future, if PSGS will be engaging in research and development that can impact national policies in keeping with the Philippine Development Plan 2023-2028, measures to improve compliance with the IRB process such as improvement of the residents' understanding of the IRB's significance in the

conduct of their research and provision of access to GCP workshops and research ethics trainings for the residents should be made.

Lack of interest in presenting and publishing their research was the second most common barrier to research productivity. Of all the causes mentioned, this one may have to be the most personal and most difficult to provide a solution for. Chances are these residents will only be complying with the research requirement for their graduation or promotion. The results shown suggest a need to have a committed consultant co-investigator other than an adviser to make sure that the residents will be able to produce and publish relevant research. Strategies to heighten their interest in research such as presentation in international research fora may also be planned. Another strategy which can also help in addressing the lack of interest in research and research presentations is to make presentations and publications mandatory for all graduating residents. This policy can also resolve other possible issues like lack of confidence and few opportunities to present their work.

In Table 7, lack of training in research methodology and lack of funding were also considered as barriers to research productivity, as mentioned by about 5% of the trainees. Only nine percent considered the lack of resources and access to a library as a hindrance to publishing their work.

This concern on lack of training has been noted by the PSGS and other surgical organizations. During the pre - covid era there were regular research workshops organized by PCS and PSGS for the trainees. These activities were stopped during the pandemic but eventually shifted to the online platform. Although helpful in providing information, a hands-on workshop would be more effective for the trainees. Hence, there is a plan to provide a learning management system not only for the trainees but

also for consultant research advisers wherein they not only learn research methods but get to work on their research as the main output of the RESEARCH module.

Table 7

Summary of Limits To Do Research

Limits to do research	N = 1014	% of total
Lack of dedicate time for research	621	61.24%
Difficult/ time consuming IRB process	123	12.13%
Lack of interest in research	89	8.78%
Lack of training in research methodology and related topics	53	5.23%
Lack of funding	49	4.83%
Lack of access to journals as reference	25	2.47%
Lack of research mentor/adviser	20	1.97%
Lack of support (research assistant)	18	1.78%
Multifactorial	15	1.48%

Table 8

Summary of Limitations in Research Presentation in a Forum

Limitations in presentation in a forum	N = 1014	% of total
Lack of time	511	50.39 %
Not interested to join	171	16.86%
Not confident about the research output	141	13.9%
Lack of opportunities for presentation	69	6.8%
Not confident to present	56	5.5%
Lack of financial support	45	4.4%
N/A	40	3.9%

Table 9*Summary of Limitations in Research Publication*

Limitations in research publication	N = 1014	% of total
Lack of time to finish the research and publish before graduation	624	61.54%
Not interested to write publication	141	13.9%
Lack of resources (access to references, library, etc.)	91	8.97%
Not confident to publish	49	4.7%
Not confident about the research output	45	4.4%
Not confident about the research output and not confident to publish	19	1.9%
Poor foundation in basics of research	1	0.1 %
Lack of funds to pay publication cost	1	0.1 %
Extensive requirements in publisher during submission for publication	1	0.1%
N/A/ waiting for approval /ongoing research /WA	41	4.04%

Institutional Factors Affecting Research Productivity**Measures of Institutional Research Productivity**

Most of the training programs were able to present only less than 10% of their research output in a forum (46/58 or 7.31%) while only 12 institutions were able to have more than 10 percent presented in a forum. However, this may not be reflective of the research productivity since the number of residents vary from one program to another. Other programs like those of DOH hospitals may have up to five residents per year level. (See Table 10)

None of the institutions were able to publish more than 50% of research output. The majority (40/58 or 69%) had less than 5% of their research published.

There is no uniform target set on research productivity – both in terms of research presentation and publications. Institutions have different targets set which are based on their respective Mission /Vision and operational plan and with the goal to attain a certain level of certification. Even the Philippine Society of General Surgeons as an organization, did not set a target with regards to the research output of the training programs. It is only in the latest PSGS curriculum that participation in scientific forum and publications will be included as an outcome measure during the accreditation of the programs. For uniformity of evaluating programs, a minimum target may need to be set by the organization- one for research presentation and another for publication. Since this initiative is still in its early stages, a lower level may be set and after a period of observation and evaluation, could be set at a higher level to boost research productivity eventually.

The study by Madan tried to investigate the percentage of papers presented in a research forum which gets to be published. Based on the review of research abstracts presented from 2009 to 2018, 51% of winning abstracts got published, mostly from surgical programs (88%) and only 26% of non-winning abstracts got published. However, factors to improve a trainee’s chance of being published remains to be determined.

Table 10

Summary of Measures of Research Productivity of the Institution

Percentage of the research output presented in a forum in a year	N = 58	% of total
</=5%	40	68.97%
6-10%	6	10.34 %
>10-50%	10	17.24%

>50%	2	3.45%
How many percent of the research output gets published per year		
</ = 5%	18	31.03%
6 - 10%	38	65.52 %
>10-50%	2	3.45%
>50%	0	0%

Facilitators of Research productivity

Established Policies on Research: Compliance with Research Agenda and Research requirement

The survey form regarding institutional factors was given to consultants who are either the designated training officer or research coordinator of their department since they are more familiar about the status of research within their department. Most of the training officers (75.9%) follow a research agenda set by their research committee as well as the research requirement set by respective Department of Medical Education Training and Research of their institutions (79%) and specialty organizations (56.9%). The research agenda may include the current NUHRA or a specific research agenda. (See Table 11).

More than half of the participating training institutions provide dedicated time for research.

Table 11

Established Policies on Research: Compliance with Research Agenda, Research requirement and Dedicated Time for Research

GS Training Program follows a research agenda	N = 58	% of total
Yes	44	75.9%
No	14	24.1 %
GS Training Program follows research requirements set by the Department of Medical Education Training and Research		
Yes	46	79.3%
No	12	20.7%
Department of Medical Education Training and Research allows the GS Training Program to follow the research requirement of their respective specialty organization		
Yes	33	56.9%
No	25	43.1%
Provision of a dedicated time for research		
Yes	32	55.2%
No	26	44.8%

Presence of Functional Research Committee

The majority of the training institutions (75.9%) have a separate research committee other than the residency training committee. Although the research committee members were noted to be active in research-related activities, 48% of them did not take further studies in research or other research-related courses.

Table 12*Presence of a Functional Department Research Committee*

Presence of a functional department research committee	N = 58	% of total
Yes	44	75.9%
No, the RTC is also in charge of research	14	24.1%
Members of the research committee active in research related activities		
Yes	45	77.6%
No	13	22.4%
Research committee members have undergone further studies related to research		
Yes	13	22.4%
Some	17	29.3%
No	28	48.3%

Availability of Research-oriented Advisers and Mentors

Table 13 presents data on the availability of research-oriented advisers and mentors. From the table, results show that most of the training institutions have research mentoring (81%), but only less than 60% of their consultant staff are involved as research advisers. Less than sixty percent of the consultant staff are actively engaged in research mentoring because of their passion for it (58.6%) or due to faculty promotion (19%). Less than sixty percent are also involved in doing their own research and were able to publish their research. The papers of Bland, 2005 and Lampman, 2003 support the finding that a research mentor or consultant who is more engaged in research is a very important facilitator of research productivity. Consultancy is key to the progress of a research up to its publication since residents are not permanent and once they graduate, they may not be able to follow up on the publication of their work.

Table 13*Availability of Research-oriented Advisers and Mentors*

Presence of research mentoring in the institution	N = 58	% of total
Yes	47	81.0%
No	11	19.0%
Percentage of the consultant staff involved as research advisers to trainees		
100	3	5.2%
90-99%	1	1.7%
80-89%	5	8.6%
70-79%	3	5.2%
60-69%	8	13.8%
below 60%	38	65.5%
Are the consultants in your institution actively engaged in research?		
Yes, they do it out of passion	34	58.6%
Yes, for promotion	11	19.0%
No	13	22.4%
Percentage of the consultant staff actively engaged in their own research		
80-89%	2	3.4%
70-79%	2	3.4%
60-69%	5	8.6%
below 60%	49	84.5%
Percentage of the consultant staff have published research		
80-89%	1	1.7%
70-79%	3	5.2%
60-69%	3	5.2%
below 60%	51	87.9%

Presence of support for Research activities (Financial, IRB, collaborations etc.)

Thirty seven out of fifty-eight training programs (63.79%) provide some form of reward or incentive for research, as seen in Table 14. This could be in the form of recognition (37.9%), funding support (8.6%) or both. However, in terms of research funding, only 41.3% of the training programs have a source of funding.

The majority (70.7 %) have their own institutional review board. They also support the attendance of the residents in various research workshops either in - house or events organized by the Philippine College of Surgeons or Philippine Society of General Surgeons (See Table 14).

In Table 15, results show that although less than half of the training programs are participating in collaborative research, an overwhelming 98% of the programs is willing to join a multi-institutional research collaboration.

Table 14

Presence of Support for Research Activities (Financial, IRB, collaborations etc.)

Presence of reward/incentive system for	N = 58	% of
Yes, award/recognition	22	37.9%
Recognition & partial funding	1	1.7%
Yes, funding support	5	8.6%
Activity attendance	1	1.7%
Yes, others	8	13.8%
None	21	36.2%
Institutional financial support for research		
Yes, full	6	10.3
Yes, partial	18	31.0
No	34	58.6

Presence of PHREB accredited IRB			
Yes	41	70.7%	
None	17	29.3%	
Do you allow the trainees to attend research		N = 58	% of
Yes, both internal and external research	33	56.9 %	
Yes	20	41.38	
No	1	1.7%	

Table 15

Current Participation of the Institution in Collaborative Surgical Research

Participation of the institution in collaborative surgical research	N = 58	% of total
No	33	56.9%
Yes	17	29.3%
Self-funded	8	13.8%
Willingness to participate in collaborative research		
Yes	57	98.3%
Maybe	1	1.7%

Analysis of Institutional factors

Type of training institution and its compliance with research agenda

A Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to assess potential differences among the different types of training institutions with regards to which programs follow a research agenda, as reported by coordinators. The results did not reveal a statistically significant effect ($\chi^2(3) = 1.562$, $p=0.668$, $\epsilon^2=0.027$). This suggests that there is no evidence of a significant difference in how programs follow a research agenda (See Appendix R).

Table 16*Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner pairwise comparisons**Pairwise comparisons - Program follow a research agenda (Coordinator)*

		W	p
Academic (University hospital)	DOH affiliated	0.285	0.997
Academic (University hospital)	Local Government Hospital	1.414	0.750
Academic (University hospital)	Private	-0.391	0.993
DOH affiliated	Local Government Hospital	1.213	0.827
DOH affiliated	Private	-0.693	0.961
Local Government Hospital	Private	-1.735	0.610

Type of training institution vs. dedicated time for research

Similarly, a Kruskal-Wallis test was also conducted to examine potential differences among the different types of training institutions. This will allow the investigator to determine which program allows dedicated time for research, as reported by coordinators. The results did not reveal a statistically significant effect ($\chi^2(3) = 5.311$, $p = 0.150$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.093$). Hence, there is no evidence of a significant difference in how programs allow dedicated time for research among the groups.

Table 17*Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner Pairwise Comparisons**Pairwise comparisons - Program allow dedicated time for research (Coordinator)*

		W	p
Academic (University hospital)	DOH affiliated	3.050	0.136
Academic (University hospital)	Local Government Hospital	2.608	0.253
Academic (University hospital)	Private	2.092	0.450
DOH affiliated	Local Government Hospital	0.108	1.000
DOH affiliated	Private	-1.094	0.867
Local Government Hospital	Private	-0.935	0.912

Type of training institution vs. institution providing financial support

A Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to explore potential differences among the different types of training institutions and whether institutions provide financial support for research, as reported by coordinators. The results did not reveal a statistically significant effect ($\chi^2(3) = 4.257, p=0.235, \epsilon^2=0.075$). This suggests that there is no evidence of a significant difference in how institutions provide financial support for research among the groups.

Table 18*Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner pairwise comparisons**Pairwise comparisons - Institution provide financial support for research**(Coordinator)*

		W	p
Academic (University hospital)	DOH affiliated	0.293	0.997
Academic (University hospital)	Local Government Hospital	-0.946	0.909
Academic (University hospital)	Private	-1.702	0.625
DOH affiliated	Local Government Hospital	-1.593	0.673
DOH affiliated	Private	-2.758	0.207
Local Government Hospital	Private	.	.

Type of training institution vs. research mentoring

A Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to investigate potential differences among the different types of training institutions regarding whether the institutions or programs have research mentoring, as reported by coordinators. The results did not show a statistically significant effect ($\chi^2(3) = 0.799, p=0.850, \epsilon^2=0.014$). This suggests that there is no evidence of a significant difference in the presence of research mentoring among the groups.

Table 19*Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner pairwise comparisons**Pairwise comparisons - Institution have research mentoring*

		W	p
Academic (University hospital)	DOH affiliated	0.041	1.000
Academic (University hospital)	Local Government Hospital	0.000	1.000
Academic (University hospital)	Private	0.975	0.901
DOH affiliated	Local Government Hospital	-0.041	1.000
DOH affiliated	Private	1.146	0.850
Local Government Hospital	Private	0.975	0.901

Type of training institution vs. committee members being active in research

To determine the potential differences among the different types of training institutions with regards to the level of research activity among the research committee members, a Kruskal-Wallis test was also conducted. The results did not reveal a statistically significant effect ($\chi^2(3) = 3.343, p=0.342, \epsilon^2=0.059$), suggesting that there is no evidence of a significant difference in the activity of the research committee members among the groups.

Table 20*Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner pairwise comparisons**Pairwise comparisons - members of the research committee active in research*

		W	p
Academic (University hospital)	DOH affiliated	-0.964	0.904
Academic (University hospital)	Local Government Hospital	-2.170	0.417
Academic (University hospital)	Private	-0.609	0.973
DOH affiliated	Local Government Hospital	-1.788	0.586
DOH affiliated	Private	0.447	0.989
Local Government Hospital	Private	2.032	0.476

Type of training institution vs. incentives

A Kruskal-Wallis test was also conducted to assess the potential differences among the different types of training institutions regarding the existence of a reward/incentive system for achievements in research. The results showed a marginally significant effect ($\chi^2(3) = 6.844$, $p = 0.077$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.120$), suggesting that there may be some evidence of variation in the presence of a reward/incentive system among the groups.

Table 21*Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner pairwise comparisons**Pairwise comparisons - reward/incentive system for achievements in research*

		W	P
Academic (University hospital)	DOH affiliated	0.556	0.979
Academic (University hospital)	Local Government Hospital	-1.622	0.661
Academic (University hospital)	Private	-1.878	0.545
DOH affiliated	Local Government Hospital	-2.610	0.252
DOH affiliated	Private	-3.290	0.092
Local Government Hospital	Private	0.379	0.993

Despite the presence of these forms of institutional support needed in the preparation and submission of research-research agenda, research mentoring, funding and incentives and dedicated time — the fact remains that time management for research is very important. A possible solution to help address this may also require funding: the employment of a research assistant or assistant within the department who can follow up on IRB submissions. With this, a decrease in the workload of the residents will allow them to start their research earlier. The need for a research assistant also came out from the survey questionnaires administered to the residents. Stricter policies on monitoring the conduct of research and setting a timeline for accomplishment of certain stages of the research may also provide guidance to the trainee and help them comply with the research publication.

Qualitative Analysis

To gain more insight on the research productivity of General Surgery training programs, taking on from the responses obtained in the qualitative part of the study, two focused group discussions (FGDs) were conducted: one among trainees (n=7) and another among the training officer or research coordinators (n=11).

The thematic analysis of the respondents focused on aspects such as significance of research in the General Surgery program, strategies and/or resources available which can foster research, barriers, and motivations to doing research, and how are they motivated to present or publish their papers. Utilizing MaxQDA for qualitative analysis, we can see in Figure 6 and Figure 7, respectively, the percentages of coded documents that were obtained for the trainees and for the training officer/ research coordinator, respectively.

Figure 6. Percentage of coded documents based on the theme as obtained from the trainees.

Figure 7. Percentage of coded documents based on the theme as obtained from the training officers/research coordinators.

A combination of close coding and in-vivo coding was utilized in analyzing the FGDs. Close coding pertains to the process of using concepts from the FGD guide questions to code the responses of the participants, while in-vivo coding involves using concepts based on the actual responses only.

The focus group discussions revealed similar responses in terms of the significance of research in the General Surgery program, strategies and resources, barriers, and motivations. They emphasized more about the strategies which can improve research productivity than the presence of barriers. One training officer considers the lack of emphasis on research as a major cause for the low productivity, hence the need to make research activities a priority also. Another training officer from a university hospital which has the infrastructure and support system for research activities said that it is the individual surgical trainees' inclination to do research which determines productivity. They have all the support systems in their institution – dedicated time, a research unit with research assistants, yet not all their residents are able to publish within the given period. This was attributed to the fact that not all surgeons are interested in research and that they just want to comply with the requirements of the training program. The trainees on the other hand said they value

Figure 9. Word cloud of responses of trainees.

Based on the thematic analysis of the FGDs, a code theory model was formed focusing on several aspects such as research as a requirement in the GS program, research productivity, motivations, hurdles to research, strategies, or resources to foster research, and research collaborations (See Figure 10).

Figure 10. Code theory model of the FGD.

When respondents were asked regarding the importance of research in their program, both trainees and training officers affirmed its importance for them individually and for the program as well. For instance, one training officer emphasized how it helps the residents prepare for further training in the field. Meanwhile, FGD among the trainees affirm its contribution to their personal career development and capacity as surgeons.

Participants were also asked regarding various strategies or resources at different levels (e.g., departmental, institutional, personal) that foster research. As such, the implementation of a research agenda, presence of research consultants and availability of funding were highlighted among different training programs. At the institutional level, the conduct of ethics review processes as well as knowledge and capacity training for the residents were observed. On the other hand, lack of available resources, capacity-building activities, and time are perceived as hurdles to research productivity. One of the trainee respondents mentioned the difficulties of doing out-of-pocket expenses to support their conference presentations and publications especially at international level. Meanwhile, a training officer observed the need to empower consultants especially on research methodologies to boost productivity in their program.

In terms of their personal motivations to continue doing research, research as a basic requirement for the completion of the program remains as a key factor for many GS residents. Having opportunities to publish as well as receiving encouragement from the consultants or the program are also seen as helpful for the residents. To further strengthen research in the training programs in the country, active collaborations and engagements across institutions is also vital. One of the training officers highlighted the difficulties of conducting collaborative research at the inter-

departmental level in their own institutions and stressed the importance of having a clear commitment to accomplish the study. Meanwhile, a trainee suggests that having a multi-center approach will be helpful in expanding the reach of a study.

Lastly, FGD participants were asked regarding the meaning of research productivity for them. Generally, they explain research productivity as one's capacity to produce publications and make presentations locally and internationally. Further, they also indicated the importance of making impactful and relevant contributions to their field.

Chapter V

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

This study evaluated the performance of General Surgery Training programs in the country as an R&D organization with regards to the status of their research productivity. The trainees' overall attitude towards research was positive with the majority having the innate interest and belief that research during training is essential. Significant volumes of research output have been completed for the purpose of meeting requirements for promotion or graduation. Although nearly half or 48% of these research outputs have been presented in a research forum, only 29.5% have been published.

With regards to research productivity, there is a difference observed among year level of training and between certain types of training institutions. Senior level residents (level IV and V) have more presentations and publications compared to the junior level residents. Residents with experience in publications during their pre-med or medicine proper have more publications during residency than their counterparts. DOH hospitals and academic institutions have more publications as compared to private hospitals.

The training programs do not differ in terms of the presence of facilitators of research productivity such as having a research agenda, dedicated time for research, functional research committee, research mentors, support for funding and other forms of support.

The trainees point out that lack of time for research is the most common factor which influence them to present or publish their scientific work. Other important

reasons contributing to fewer research presentations and publications among General Surgery residents include lack of training in research, the difficult IRB process and lack of committed research advisers.

The study was able to prove our conceptual framework that personal as well as institutional factors can affect research productivity. Among the personal factors, the individual's interest, and motivation to do research, prior research publication experience, and length of training which can be considered facilitators of productivity. For the institutional factors analyzed, although there was no difference among training programs with regards to the presence of identified facilitators of research, these did not translate to maximal research productivity. This proves the point that success in scientific research and R&D requires a synergistic interaction among the researchers and the other systems: technical subsystem, the management and other support systems (Reyes, J., 1995). In an R&D organization, the creative researcher scientist does not only need the motivation and stimulus to conduct research, he or she needs a conducive environment to carry out research. Research in the field of surgery can be complicated, expensive and resource intensive. Administration or management should not expect much research productivity from surgical trainees faced with time and resource constraints to complete their research up to publication. Instead, the surgical training programs would have to invest their resources – time, effort, financial, human resource and others to create a plausible adaptive surgical research program which can harness and direct the efforts of the surgeon trainee to engage in relevant research and can support the research initiatives from conception, implementation to publication producing research that is aligned with an agenda that is supportive of the nation's development plan.

Creating a sustainable research program can put together personal and institutional factors and ensure a progressive and sustained research productivity translating research to innovation, not only for the institution but more importantly, could contribute to the needs of society thereby strengthening the role of surgical programs in the nations' research and development, technology and innovation progress.

With the findings from this analysis, the proposed conceptual framework is thus revised as follows:

Figure 11. Revised conceptual framework.

Recommendations

To achieve research productivity, first, it would be essential for the surgical specialty organization, particularly PSGS and its member training programs, to recognize its role in research and development not only within the surgical community but in the society. In the current set up, the General surgical programs and institutions are primarily healthcare providers and secondly, training institutions. Their role as knowledge creators, researchers, innovators is underemphasized and not considered a priority hence there is limited resource and support provided for this aspect.

Second, the organization should be made aware of the interplay of the facilitators and barriers to research productivity as elucidated in the study so as help them plan next steps which include :establishing a framework of support, encouraging research collaborations among its training programs and implementing strategies that could assist and motivate the institutions and their trainees to engage in relevant and quality research publications with improved research utilization that can have an impact on surgical care and national policies thereby contributing to societal development .

For the concrete actions, the very first step to improve research productivity among the General Surgery training programs of PSGS is for the organization to **communicate** the importance of its role as an R&D organization which is expected to produce relevant and quality research aligned with a national surgical research agenda. The researcher should be made aware of the importance of their role as researcher and how they can contribute to national development. This could help motivate them and improve their interest in the activity.

Another concrete action is to **organize** a meeting participated in by key stakeholders and key resource persons to **establish a feasible National Surgical**

Research Agenda which will be cascaded to the programs and subspecialty organizations. This would help ensure that the research produced by the programs are aligned towards answering specific knowledge gaps and would be useful in the general landscape of improving surgical care. This could also promote collaborative research among institutions and specialty organizations that could produce national data which could be applied to further improve healthcare.

Since it has been pointed out that lack of dedicated time and training in research methodology are the important factors affecting residents' ability to present and publish their research, it is recommended to **create a basic research program** which includes scheduled workshops, an organized timeline of submission, and identification of well-equipped and committed research advisers to guide the residents. There is currently a research program deployed using the Philippine College of Surgeons Learning Management System called Research Education for Scientific Excellence: A Research Capacity Hub (R.E.S.E.A.R.CH.) initiated by the PSGS Committee on Research in collaboration with the PCS Committee on Research and Innovation, PCS LMS Committee and the Philippine Association of Training Officers in Surgery, Inc. This is intended not only for the residents but also for consultants who would be the advisers to improve their research knowledge and capabilities and foster early collaboration between trainees and consultants since they will be working together on their project (See Appendix X). To make this program work, strict **implementation, monitoring** and **evaluation** methods should be put in place. Future studies to evaluate the improvement in research productivity after these strategies have been implemented are recommended.

Aside from the research program, the surgical societies have also included **opportunities for presentation** of research during their conventions through research contests, posters, and free paper sessions. The current study was not able to consider which type of research are favorably published and whether the publications were in local or international journals which can be done in future studies.

Another important factor in research productivity is the support system namely, the finance-management system and technical system. The **establishment of a clinical research unit** within the department or institution with the **personnel** to assist the researcher (secretary, encoder, etc.) with regards to administrative matters (IRB application forms, budget preparation, grant applications etc.) and technical matters (research assistant, statistician, laboratory assistant, technical writer) would be very helpful for the researcher who can now focus and use his time in conducting the research and in meeting publication requirements. The clinical research unit should also have the necessary **infrastructure and equipment** – computers, internet connection, lab facilities. In addition. **Funding** that will support research endeavors should be made accessible, if not available, to the researcher.

There may be so many things to do before the aspired productivity can be achieved, but if the organization believes in the importance of its role as an R& D organization in nation building, it will start moving towards the direction of **improving the research culture among its programs and institutions.**

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APPENDIX A

Sampling frame for the General Surgery residents

Number of Residents as of June 2023

1st year - 273
 2nd year - 180
 3rd year - 193
 4th year - 199
 5th year - 227
 Total: 1,072

Sample Size for Frequency in a Population

Population size(for finite population correction factor or fpc)(N): 1072
 Hypothesized % frequency of outcome factor in the population (p):20%+/-5
 Confidence limits as % of 100(absolute +/- %)(d): 5%
 Design effect (for cluster surveys-DEFF): 1

Sample Size(n) for Various Confidence Levels

ConfidenceLevel(%)	Sample Size
95%	201
80%	96
90%	150
97%	236
99%	305
99.9%	422
99.99%	510

Equation

Sample size $n = [DEFF * N * p(1-p)] / [(d^2 / Z^2 * 1 - \alpha/2 * (N-1) + p * (1-p)]$

Results from OpenEpi, Version 3, open source calculator--SSPropor
 Print from the browser with ctrl-P
 or select text to copy and paste to other programs.

APPENDIX B

Sampling frame for the training/ research coordinators

- 71 Accredited Training Programs
- 71 research coordinators

Sample Size for Frequency in a Population

Population size(for finite population correction factor or fpc)(N):	71
Hypothesized % frequency of outcome factor in the population (p):	20%+/-5
Confidence limits as % of 100(absolute +/- %)(d):	5%
Design effect (for cluster surveys-DEFF):	1

Sample Size(n) for Various Confidence Levels

ConfidenceLevel(%)	Sample Size
95%	56
80%	43
90%	51
97%	58
99%	61
99.9%	65
99.99%	67

Equation

$$\text{Sample size } n = [\text{DEFF} * Np(1-p)] / [(d^2 / Z^2_{1-\alpha/2} * (N-1) + p*(1-p)]$$

Results from OpenEpi, Version 3, open source calculator--SSPropor
Print from the browser with ctrl-P
or select text to copy and paste to other programs.

APPENDIX C

General Surgery Trainee Survey Form

INDIVIDUAL PERSONAL FACTORS (To be answered by the surgical trainee)

Socio- Demographics

Age: _____

Sex at birth

___ Male ___ Female

Pre-Med Course:

___ Science related (Bio, Zoo, Psych, Nursing, Med tech etc) (make drop down, with OTHERS)

___ Non- science related Please specify _____

Type of Training Institution where they are undergoing training (put description)

___ Academic (University hospital)

___ DOH affiliated

___ Private

___ Local Government Hospital

Training Program (if the resident is rotating only in GS but will be going to a subspecialty, check both GS and the subspecialty)

___ General Surgery

___ Orthopedic Surgery

___ Neurosurgery

___ Otorhinolaryngology

___ Pediatric Surgery

___ Obstetrics and Gynecology

___ Plastic & Reconstructive Surgery

___ Ophthalmology

___ TCVS

___ Urology

Current Year Level of training

___ I

___ IV

___ II

___ V

___ III

___ VI

What do think about doing research work during training? (check all that applies)

___ essential

___ provides opportunities

___ helps improve patient care

___ improves chances of being employed

after training or getting into fellowship. ___ rewarding

___ eats up time dedicated to patient care

___ unnecessary effort

___ promotes self - efficacy

___ consumes resource

Others, please specify _____

Where do the trainees get ideas for their research?

___ research adviser

___ books

___ curiosity

___ from journals we read

___ cases encountered

Did you have Research subject during medicine proper?

___ Yes

___ No

If Yes, what is / are this/ these subject/s?

Did you have any publications during pre-med

___ Yes _____ No

If Yes, what type?

___ poster paper

___ journal article

___ chapter in a book

___ brochures

___ others

Did you have any publications during Medicine proper? (poster, printed, oral presentation)

___ Yes _____ No

If Yes, what

___ poster paper

___ journal article

___ chapter in a book

___ brochures

___ others

During residency, in one training year, how many times have you presented your research in a forum?

___ once _____ twice _____ thrice. _____ more than thrice

How many research were you able to publish during training?

___ one _____ two _____ three _____ more than three

(**may have more than one answer**)

1. What limits your presentation in a forum

1. _____ not interested to join

2. _____ lack time

3. _____ not confident about the research output

4. _____ not confident to present

5. _____ others

2. What limits your research publication? (may have more than one answer)

1. _____ not interested

2. _____ lack time to finish the research and publish before graduation

3. _____ Lack of resources (access to references, library etc)

4. _____ not confident about the research output

5. _____ not confident to publish

6. _____ others

What do you think is research productivity?

What do you recommend to improve research productivity?

Thank you.

APPENDIX D

Consultant/Research Coordinator Survey Form

TO BE ANSWERED BY THE TRAINING OFFICER OR RESEARCH COORDINATOR PER INSTITUTION

_____ **NAME OF INSTITUTION**

_____ **email**

I. Demographics

Sex at birth

___ Male ___ Female

Age range _____

30- 40

41-50

51-60

>60

II. Type of Training Institution

___ Academic (University hospital)

___ Private

___ DOH affiliated

___ Local Government

Hospital

Type Of Training Program available in the institution (check all that applies)

___ General Surgery

___ Obstetrics and

Gynecology ___ Ophthalmology

___ Pediatric

Surgery ___ Orthopedic Surgery

___ TCVS

___ Plastic & Reconstructive Surgery

___ Neurosurgery

___ Urology

III. Research Policies of the Institution:

i. Does your program follow a research agenda?

___ Yes

___ NO

Explain _____

ii. Research requirements

1. Is the research requirement of your training program based on the requirements by the Department of Medical Education Training and Research of your institution

___ Yes ___ No

Why Not? _____

2. Does your Department of Medical Education, Training and Research Office follow the research requirement of your respective specialty organization?

___ Yes ___ No

Why Not? _____

3. Does your department of surgery/ institution's research policy require trainees to have a research output for every year of training?

_____ Yes

_____ No

If not, how many research are required for graduation _____
_____ at least 1-----at least 2____at least 3_____ other

4. In a training year, how many research was presented in a forum?

a. ≤ 5

b. 6-10

c. >10- 50%

d. >50%

5. How many percent of the research output gets published per year?

a. ≤ 5 %

b. 6- 10%

c. >10- 50%

d. >50%

iii. Does the program allow dedicated time for research?

_____ Yes

_____ No

If yes, how many hours per week?

_____ ≤ 5 hours_

_____ > 24 hours

_____ 5-10 hours

_____ 11-24 hours_

_____ others

iv. Does your institution provide financial support for research?

_____ yes, full

_____ yes, partial

_____ NO

If you answered yes please respond to the ff:

Is the financial support provided by your institution unconditional, meaning, it is given to all regardless of the quality of the protocol?

_____ yes

_____ No, there is a given criterion before a researcher is given support

v. Does your institution/ program have research mentoring?

_____ Yes

_____ No

Please explain _____

E2. Are the consultants in your institution actively engaged in research

_____ yes, they need research to be promoted

_____ yes, they do it out of passion

_____ no

vi. Does your institution have a PHREB accredited IRB?

_____ Yes

_____ None

_____ submit to external IRB

vii. Do you allow the trainees to attend research workshops regularly?

If YES,

_____regularly _____occasionally

_____yes , in house

_____yes, they are supported to attend external conducted workshops by PCS,PSGS

_____yes, both internal and external research workshops(by PCS, PSGS)

_____If No, Why not _____

viii. Participation in collaborative/ multi institutional research

1. Is your institution currently participating in collaborative surgical research

_____Yes

_____co-authorship

_____sharing of resources

_____lab use

_____sponsorship for training

_____others, specify

If yes _____self funded (in house)

_____with funding source (external)

_____If Not engaged in collaborative research

Why Not?

2. Will your department/institution agree to participate in collaborative research to establish national data?

_____Yes

_____Maybe Explain why or what will make you join ?

_____No. Why Not? (check all that applies)

_____time constraints

_____lack of human resources/personnel

_____data privacy constraints

_____others, please specify

ix. Qualifications of the research adviser/mentor

1. Do you have a department research committee?

_____Yes

_____No, the RTC is also in charge of research

2. Are the members of the research committee active in research (attending research workshops, involved as advisers, doing their own research?)

_____Yes

_____No

3. Do the members of the research committee undergo/ undergone further studies related to research (ex .Clinical epidemiology, master's in research , etc)

- Yes, all of them
- Some of them
- None

4. What percentage of the consultant staff are involved as research advisers to trainees?

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> 96% - 100% | <input type="checkbox"/> 81%- 85% |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 91% - 95% | <input type="checkbox"/> 76-80% |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 86% - 90 % | <input type="checkbox"/> below 75% |

5. What percentage of the consultant staff are actively engaged in their own research

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> 96% - 100% | <input type="checkbox"/> 81%- 85% |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 91% - 95% | <input type="checkbox"/> 76-80% |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 86% - 90 % | <input type="checkbox"/> below 75% |

6. What percentage of the consultant staff have published research ?

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> 96% - 100% | <input type="checkbox"/> 81%- 85% |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 91% - 95% | <input type="checkbox"/> 76-80% |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 86% - 90 % | <input type="checkbox"/> below 75% |

x. Do you have a reward/incentive system for achievements in research?

- yes
 - award/recognition
 - funding support
 - others , please specify
- none

APPENDIX E

Institutional Review Board Approval

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Health
JOSE R. REYES MEMORIAL MEDICAL CENTER
Rizal Avenue, Sta. Cruz, Manila 1003
☎ 7321071-76 loc. 296 🌐 <http://www.jrmmc.org> 📧 irb@jrmmc.gov.ph

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD

Form 2.7

APPROVAL LETTER

June 7, 2023

This is to certify that the following protocol and related documents have been granted approval by the Jose R. Reyes Memorial Medical Center IRB for implementation.

IRB Protocol No.	2023-044	Sponsor Protocol No.	
Principal Investigator/s	IDA MARIE T. LIM, MD	Sponsor	
Title	Factors affecting Research Productivity of Surgical Trainees in the Philippines: An Analytical Cross-sectional Study		
Protocol Version No.	0	Version Date	May 23, 2023
ICF Version No.	0	Version Date	May 23, 2023
Other Documents			
Type of Review	<input type="checkbox"/> Expedited <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Full board Approval date: May 31, 2023	Duration of Approval: May 31, 2023 May 30, 2024	Frequency of Continuing Review: Once a year

Investigator Responsibilities after Approval:

- Submit document amendments for IRB approval before implementing them.
- Submit the SAE and SUSAR reports to the IRB within 7 days.
- Submit the progress report every 12 months.
- Submit the final report after completion of protocol procedures at the study site.
- Report protocol deviation/violation.
- Comply with all relevant international and national guidelines and regulations.
- Abide by the principles of good clinical practice and ethical research.
- This approval is valid for a period of one year from the date of issue. Therefore, the PI must re-apply for continuing ethics review.

*The Jose R. Reyes Memorial Medical Center Institutional Review Board is organized and operates according to the **Good Clinical Practice** and all applicable laws and regulations.*

IRB Chairperson	Signature	Date
MICHELLE Y. OTAYCO, MD, FPCP, FPSN, MMHoA		06/07/2023

Received by:

Name & Signature: _____

Date: _____

APPENDIX F

Difference in research productivity (number of times presented research in a forum) among different year levels of training

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric). Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
No. of times presented in a research forum	81.292	6	<.001	0.080

APPENDIX G

Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner pairwise comparisons
Pairwise comparisons - No. of times presented in a research forum

		W	p
III	I	-7.280	<0.001
III	II	-1.129	0.985
III	IV	2.617	0.514
III	V	3.084	0.306
III	VI	1.768	0.874
III	VII	2.757	0.448
I	II	6.205	<0.001
I	IV	10.100	<0.001
I	V	10.748	<0.001
I	VI	4.042	0.065
I	VII	3.623	0.138
II	IV	3.850	0.093
II	V	4.368	0.033
II	VI	2.184	0.718
II	VII	2.967	0.354
IV	V	0.393	1.000
IV	VI	1.039	0.990
IV	VII	2.628	0.509
V	VI	0.953	0.994
V	VII	2.682	0.483
VI	VII	1.571	0.925

APPENDIX H

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric) Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
Publication during training	37.548	6	<.001	0.037

1.

APPENDIX I

Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner pairwise comparisons
 Pairwise comparisons - Publish during training (Trainees)

		W	p
III	I	-3.645	0.133
III	II	-0.432	1.000
III	IV	1.780	0.871
III	V	4.041	0.065
III	VI	-0.869	0.996
III	VII	2.723	0.463
I	II	3.130	0.288
I	IV	5.562	0.002
I	V	7.715	< .001
I	VI	0.118	1.000
I	VII	3.878	0.088
II	IV	2.187	0.717
II	V	4.379	0.032
II	VI	-0.744	0.998
II	VII	2.872	0.395
IV	V	2.423	0.607
IV	VI	-1.355	0.963
IV	VII	2.264	0.682
V	VI	-1.944	0.816
V	VII	1.531	0.933
VI	VII	2.289	0.671

APPENDIX J

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric)
Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
No. of times presented research in a forum	10.613	3	0.014	0.010

2.

APPENDIX K

Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner pairwise comparisons

Pairwise comparisons – No. of times presented research in a forum

		W	p
Academic (University hospital)	DOH affiliated	1.084	0.870
Academic (University hospital)	Local Government Hospital	2.546	0.273
Academic (University hospital)	Private	3.994	0.025
DOH affiliated	Local Government Hospital	1.838	0.563
DOH affiliated	Private	3.582	0.055
Local Government Hospital	Private	1.288	0.799

APPENDIX L

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric).Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
Publication during training (Trainees)	4.481	3	0.214	0.004

3.

APPENDIX M

Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner pairwise comparisons

Pairwise comparisons - Publish during training (Trainees)

		W	p
Academic (University hospital)	DOH affiliated	1.068	0.875
Academic (University hospital)	Local Government Hospital	0.086	1.000
Academic (University hospital)	Private	2.578	0.263
DOH affiliated	Local Government Hospital	-0.907	0.919
DOH affiliated	Private	1.868	0.550
Local Government Hospital	Private	2.345	0.346

APPENDIX N

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric). Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
No. of times presented research in a forum	0.014	1	0.907	0.000

APPENDIX O

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric). Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p
Publications during training	0.003	1	0.957

APPENDIX P

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric). Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p
Times have you presented your research in a forum	2.380	1	0.123

APPENDIX Q

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric). Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p	ξ^2
Publications during training	10.236	1	0.001	0.010

APPENDIX R

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric). Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
Program follow a research agenda (Coordinator)	1.562	3	0.668	0.027

APPENDIX S

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric). Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
Program allow dedicated time for research (Coordinator)	5.311	3	0.150	0.093

APPENDIX T

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric).

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
Institution provide financial support for research (Coordinator)	4.257	3	0.235	0.075

APPENDIX U

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric).

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
Institution/program have research mentoring (Coordinator)	0.799	3	0.850	0.014

APPENDIX V

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric).

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
Members of the research committee active in research	3.343	3	0.342	0.059

APPENDIX W

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric).

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
Reward/incentive system for achievements in research	6.844	3	0.077	0.120

APPENDIX X

Research Education for Scientific Excellence: a Research Capacity Hub (R.E.S.E.A.R.C.H.)

GUIDE TO ONLINE LEARNING ACTIVITIES

DESCRIPTION

This modular course will serve as a research capacity hub with a constructively aligned, researcher-centered, outcomes-based curriculum consistent with the 2023 PSGS curriculum.

This aims to assist the PSGS and its training programs to achieve one of the program outcomes for trainees – Proficiency as a RESEARCHER, one who is proficient in conducting relevant and timely research activities as part of patient care, academic and professional pursuits, surgical advancement, and innovation and promote research productivity eventually.

The government has published the Philippine **Development Plan for 2023 to 2028** and included it as a target under Outcomes 4' Health Systems Strengthened is “strengthening health research for evidence-informed policymaking and self-sufficiency in health technology. Through this capacity building, we hope our specialty organization can contribute to the government’s goal.

Through timely conduct of learning sessions, it is hoped that the following key performance indicators will be achieved

KPI's

- Able to competently formulate the research question, related hypothesis, and objectives to start a research protocol
- Perform an efficient search of the medical literature in line with research protocol writing and for evidence-based medicine
- Complete:
 - Case report
 - Research proposal/protocol
 - Research paper abstract and manuscript
- Presentation of a scientific abstract/ paper
- Publish a scientific article

Submission of Tasks

1. For first years :

a. Formulation of the research question, Hypothesis, and Objectives for their proposed research

This must be submitted via email to admin_lms@pcs.org.ph on or before the specified submission date- **April 30, 2024**

SUBMISSION FORMAT: institution. Year level. surname, first name

The resident will also present and discuss the output with their research adviser/ coordinator in their respective institution for checking.

The combined output of the trainee and consultant adviser will be presented during a face-to-face workshop on **July 30, 2024**, before the main PATOS Convention during the PSGS Surgical Forum.

- b. The second output is the **abstract of a case report, which the resident must complete during his first year of training**, to be submitted on or before, **October 31, 2024**.

2. For higher-level residents, complex tasks include the following:

a. Research protocol proposal – for second and third years

The proposal should follow the prescribed IRB format and include the informed consent form.

This must be submitted via email to admin_lms@pcs.org.ph on or before the specified submission date, **October 31, 2024**.

SUBMISSION FORMAT: institution. Year level. surname, first name

The consultant adviser should check this and it will be discussed during the PATOS pre-convention workshop on **July 30, 2024**.

b. Scientific abstract –fourth and fifth-year residents

The scientific abstract should follow the usual guidelines used by organizations in abstract submission.

(250- 350 words with the following parts: Introduction and Objectives, Methods, Results, Conclusion)

This must be submitted via email to admin_lms@pcs.org.ph on or before the specified submission date, **July 30, 2024**.

SUBMISSION FORMAT: institution. Year level. surname, first name

The consultant adviser should check this and will be discussed during the PATOS pre-convention workshop on **July 30, 2024**

c. All output must be counterchecked by the research adviser from your institution.

APPENDIX Y
Proposed Research Curriculum

PSGS Outcomes Based Curriculum (2023)

Previous Program Outcomes Corresponding to Surgeon's Roles

PROGRAM OUTCOMES/ SURGEON'S ROLES	CORRESPONDING OUTCOMES DERIVED FROM THE CHED MEMORANDUM ENCOMPASSED BY THE SURGEON'S ROLE
<p>Clinician</p> <p>1. Proficient and safe surgeon</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Clinical decision making and judgment -Technical proficiency and intra-operative judgment - Efficient communicator <p>2. Ethical and professional surgeon</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Demonstrate clinical competence · Communicate effectively · <i>Engage in research activities</i> · Collaborates with interprofessional teams · Engage in continuing personal and professional development · Adhere to ethical, professional, and legal standard
<p>Educator</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Demonstrate clinical competence · Engage in research activities · Communicate effectively
<p>Health and Social Advocate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Utilize system-based approach to healthcare · Lead and manage healthcare teams · Collaborates with interprofessional teams · Communicate effectively · Adhere to ethical, professional, and legal standards · Demonstrate nationalism, internationalism, and dedication to service · Create models and processes of social accountability
<p>Leader/ Manager</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Lead and manage healthcare teams · Collaborates with interprofessional teams · Communicate effectively · Utilize system-based approach to healthcare · Demonstrate nationalism, internationalism, and dedication to service · Create models and processes of social accountability
<p>Efficient communicator</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Communicate effectively · Demonstrate clinical competence · Adhere to ethical, professional, and legal standards · Collaborates with interprofessional teams

Researcher	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Engage in research activities · Demonstrate clinical competence · Communicate effectively · Collaborates with interprofessional teams
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Competency standard

RESEARCHER	<p>i. Independently write, implement, and present research protocols/ innovations in local and/or international fora</p> <p>ii. Incorporates principles of evidence-based medicine in the acquisition of knowledge and application to patient care and decision making</p> <p>Suggested Revision: collaborate with other professionals in the development, conduct and publication of research which can eventually influence institutional and national policies</p>
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Key Performance Indicators

<p>RESEARCHER</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Able to competently search the literature, appraise journals and apply the concepts that are relevant to patient care and management · Complete attendance to research related courses, including, but not limited to, the following: research methodology, critical appraisal, good clinical practice · Write: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Case report - Research proposal/protocol - Research paper · Presentation of a research paper (local/national or international) <p>Suggested Revision Two KPI's</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Utilization and application of research in patient care and management (corresponds to bullet 1) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Literature search b. Journal appraisal 2. Engagement in Research development <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Research protocol development b. Clinical research output(Case report, descriptive study analytical study, qualitative study, meta-analysis) 3. Research publication <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Research presentation b. publication in scientific journal <p>*the attendance to courses are learning activities</p>
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Proposed Instructional Design

I. Research Protocol Development (Mainly Year levels 1-3)

Intended Learning Outcomes	Course Content	Learning activities	Year Level to engage in learning activities	Assessment task	Deadline to complete task
Formulate research question, objectives, hypothesis, and conceptual framework for a research project	Sources and criteria for good research ideas Components of a good research question "PICOM" Research objectives a. Purpose b. Characteristics Hypothesis c. Purpose d. Characteristics Conceptual framework	LMS workshop	All But should start at year level 1	Exercise on research question formulation applying the research topics they want to work on (to be checked by research adviser/ co-investigator)	Year level 1
Conduct a systematic literature search using Pubmed	Searching the literature Pubmed search	LMS	All	RRL for approved research proposal	Year level 2

Draft a completed research protocol/proposal	<p>Overview of research designs General categories:</p> <p>A .Qualitative Overview of Qualitative Research Design</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Types of Research Design 2. Data collection tools 3. Data Analysis <p>B. Quantitative:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Descriptive 2. Analytic <p>Four basic research designs a. Cross-sectional b. Case-control studies c. Cohort studies Controlled trials</p>	LMS	<p>All but should start at year level 1 (case report and meta-analysis)</p> <p>Year level 2 (higher year levels may brush up on the topics)</p> <p>Quantitative Research designs</p> <p>Year level 3 and up Qualitative designs</p>	<p>Research protocol ready for IRB submission</p> <p>IRB approved research protocol</p>	Year level 3 (first quarter)
Construct appropriate questionnaire as a data gathering instrument	Basics in constructing and evaluating self-reported measures (e.g., questionnaire) and other data collection tools	LMS workshop	Year level 2 and 3	Sample questionnaire for their research	Year level 2
Design an informed consent form based on sound ethical principles	Ethics in research a. Ethical principles in research Informed consent	LMS workshop	All	Informed consent part of the IRB submission	Year level 2

II. Conduct of Research and Research publication

Intended Learning Outcomes	Course Content	Learning activities	Year Level to engage in learning activities	Assessment task	Deadline to complete
Utilize a professionally designed, feasible, relevant, and ethical research protocol in the conduct of research. (Continued from previous year levels)	Scientifically sound and IRB approved research proposal. Compliant with research agenda of the institution	Actual conduct of research Data collection Compliance with Health research ethics	Starting at year level 3 up to 5 Year level 1 and 2 may be assigned as co-investigators. Year level 1 -2 (completed case report) Year level 3 (may do a meta-analysis) Year level 4-5 Should have completed clinical research using IRB approved protocol	Regular updates with Research adviser and Research coordinator of the department	Year 3-5

<p>Conduct and finish relevant health research according to principles of Research Ethics</p>	<p>IRB approved Research Protocol Informed Consent forms Budget Study setting</p> <p>Manuscript: Objectives Methods Results Data analysis Statistical analysis Discussion Conclusion and Recommendations</p> <p>b. Informed consent process and documentation</p> <p>c. Data gathering</p>	<p>Actual conduct of research with supervision by research advisers and consultant co-investigators</p>	<p>Starting at year level 3 up to 5</p> <p>Year level 1 and 2 may be assigned as co-investigators.</p> <p>Year level 1 -2 completed case report</p> <p>Year level 3 (may do a meta analysis)</p> <p>Year level 4-5 Should have completed clinical research using IRB approved protocol</p>	<p>Regular updates with Research adviser and Research coordinator of the department</p>	<p>Year 3-5</p>
<p>Presentation/Publication of completed research</p>	<p>Manuscript writing</p> <p>Abstract writing</p>	<p>LMS Workshop</p>	<p>Year level 4 and 5</p>	<p>Submission of abstracts and papers to relevant Research Fora</p>	<p>ALL Year level 1-2 case report</p> <p>Year level 3- meta-analysis (optional)</p> <p>Year level 4-5 Clinical research</p>

III. Utilization and application of Research in Patient Care and Management

Intended Learning Outcomes	Course Content	Learning activities	Year Level to engage in learning activities	Assessment task
Do critical appraisal of a chosen/assigned scientific article on the following aspects of managing a clinical condition: diagnosis, therapy, harm, prognosis,	<p>Concepts and principles of Evidence based Medicine and Critical appraisal of the medical literature.</p> <p>Criteria for validity of a given research design.</p>	<p>LMS</p> <p>Critical appraisal series</p>	Year level 2 and 3	<p>Journal club</p> <p>Application of EBM in Case discussions</p>

IV. A. Proposal for Schedule of Research related Learning activities (LMS)

	First quarter	First Quarter	First Quarter	Second Quarter	Second Quarter	Third Quarter	Fourth Quarter
	Formulate research question, objectives, hypothesis, and conceptual framework	How to Write a Case Report	Research Ethics/ GCP	Basic Research Methodology	How to make a Systematic Review and Meta-analysis	Manuscript Writing	Getting Published
First Year	priority	priority	priority	/	/	/	
Second year	priority	priority	priority	/	/	/	
Third year	priority	optional	priority	/	priority	priority	priority
Fourth year		optional	Optional if expired	/	/	priority	priority
Fifth year		optional	Optional if expired	/	/	priority	priority

B. RESEARCH OUTPUT BY YEAR LEVEL

Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	After Graduation
1. Case Report	Should have finished case report and submit it for presentation/publication	Published Case report	/	/	publications
2. Prepare a research protocol which he/she will work on up to graduation	2. Apply for IRB approval; get a first year as co-investigator	Approved by IRB and start working on the research		Completed research	
3. Be a co-investigator to a current second year	Continue research	May have finished one research as co-investigator; If paper needs to be continued, may work on it till 5 th year	May have finished one research as co-investigator; If paper needs to be continued, may work on it till 5 th year	Published the research	

C.PSGS National Research Agenda Setting (see reference material)

1. Draft a letter for the training programs and general surgery subspecialties (HPB, Breast, Head and Neck, Hernia, Colorectal, Surgical Oncology, MIS).
2. Determine their research priorities
 - C. Identified knowledge gaps of those who are part of CPG's
 - D. Common surgical conditions
 - E. Emerging trends/ innovations
 - F. NUHRA
 - G. Others
3. Come up with guideline for collaborative research (look into research curriculum)